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ANNUAL REPORT
OF THE
ARCHAEOLOGICAL DEPARTMENT
GWALIOR STATE
FOR
YEAR 1924-25, V. SAMVAT 1981.

GWALIOR:
ALIJAH DARBAR PRESS.

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ANNUAL ADMINISTRATION REPORT
OF THE
ARCHÆOLOGICAL DEPARTMENT, GWALIOR STATE

FOR
The Year ending 30th June 1925, Samvat 1981.

PART I.

I. OFFICE NOTES.

1. **Charge.**—During the year of report the undersigned held charge of the Department except from the 1st to the 19th of July, while he was on privilege leave. During the period of leave, the charge of the current duties of the post remained with R. S. Saksena, the Archæological Overseer.

2. **Leave.**—The Superintendent availed himself of 19 days' privilege leave in continuation of similar leave which he enjoyed at the end of the preceding year.

Members of the subordinate staff enjoyed leave as follows :—

(a) Photographer-Draughtsman—privilege leave of 22 days from the 9th to the 30th June 1925 and sick leave on medical certificate for 9 days from the 1st to the 9th July 1924.

(b) General Assistant—privilege leave for 30 days from the 1st to the 9th July and from the 14th November to the 4th December 1924.

(c) Officer Sarishta—privilege leave for 17 days in all, in the months of July, August and September 1924.

3. **New Post.**—Hitherto one and the same clerk used to manage the correspondence and record work in this office. But with the increase of work this task began to prove increasingly difficult and systematic work became almost impossible. In response to my representation the Darbar were pleased to sanction a record-keeper's post in the year of report.

4. **General.**—All the office staff discharged their respective duties harmoniously, diligently and carefully for which I am glad to record my appreciation.

Home Member Sahib inspected this office on the 4th of May and the general impression he carried as a result of the inspection is recorded by him in the Inspection Book as follows:—

दफ्तर का काम बने अच्छा पाया. सुपरिन्टेन्डेंट साहब काम में दिव्यचरणी और मेहनत करते हैं. इनका अमला भी होशियार और मेहनती मालूम हुआ, खास करके इनका एहकार खंडालकर यह काबिल तरकी है. किसी दूसरे महकमे में जगह ज्यादा मुशाहिरे की खाली हुई, तो इसको जरूर मौका दिया जाना चाहिये.

II. Circulars and Orders.

5. No Circulars or Departmental Orders with special reference to this Department, were issued in the year of report.

III. Work at Headquarters.

6. In addition to the ordinary routine of office the following work was done during the headquarter season:—

- (a) Annual Administration Report for Samvat 1980 was drawn up and submitted.
- (b) A resume of the Conservation and Exploration accomplished by the Department in the year 1923-24 (Samvat 1980) was contributed to the *Annual Report of the Archaeological Survey of India*.
- (c) An illustrated article on Chanderi was contributed to the Birthday Special Number of the *Jayaji Pratap*.
- (d) A number of lantern slides were prepared to supplement the previous collection.
- (e) New acquisitions brought into the Archaeological Museum were arranged and labelled.
- (f) A Hindi translation of the *Gwalior Fort Album* was prepared and published.
- (g) A detailed Circular for the preservation of Ancient Monuments in this State was drafted.
- (h) Magic lantern shows illustrating the Archæological monuments and sculptures in the State were given at two local centres of the Ganapati festival.

IV. Tours.

7. During the year under report I spent 124 days in camp, partly for

- (a) Listing monuments.
- (b) Annual inspection of the principal groups of monuments conserved already.
- (c) Supervising and directing the works of conservation in progress.
- (d) Collecting material and taking necessary photographs for the proposed publication of *A Guide to Chanderi*.
- (e) Carrying out excavations at Pawaya.

8. The following places were visited for listing monuments:—Khanpura, Naderi, Gurilako Pahad, Lakhari, Bithla and Rakhetra or Gadbelna. Visits of annual inspection were paid to conserved monuments at Gwalior, Bhilsa, Besnagar, Udaygiri, Badoh, Chanderi, Fatehabad, Ujjain, Bagh, Narwar and Surwaya. I visited Bagh and Chanderi each twice and Narwar four times in order to direct the conservation work in progress there. I also visited Udaypur, Budhi Chanderi, Mandasor, Sondni and Khilchipura in connection with the proposed conservation of the monuments at these places. I encamped at Pawaya for over two weeks in all during four visits in order to supervise and direct the excavation works at this ancient site, and at Chanderi for a week in order to collect material for the proposed publication of an illustrated Guide to this place. Detailed Diary of the tour is given in Appendix A.

9. During the year of report Sir John Marshall, the Director-General of Archæology in India, paid a visit to Bagh Caves. Dr. J. H. Cousins; the well-known art critic, also visited these Caves in my company.

V. Conservation.

10. Conservation work was carried out at the following places at a total expenditure of Rs. 29,534-1-0 including the special grant for Narwar Fort :—

1. **Bagh** (District Amjhera).—The work of clearing debris from the Buddhist caves which had been going on for the last three years was brought to a completion. The work in cave No. 4 was specially difficult as it was also important. The main hall and the surrounding corridors were filled up almost to the ceiling with huge blocks of rock partly consisting of decayed pillars and partly fallen from the ceiling. The monolithic pillars supporting the ceiling, having disappeared for the most part, large spans of ceiling are overhanging and threatening to come down at any moment. To work under them was therefore attended with considerable danger. A small portion of the ceiling did come down, in spite of careful precautions, while the labourers were working below; but fortunately nobody was hurt and the work was completed without any serious mishap. A small portion of debris still remains inside cave No. 4 as it is dangerous to remove it unless the ceiling is re-supported on masonry pillars.

11. Last year a mound of debris in the joint verandah of caves Nos. 4 and 5 had been left over to serve as a scaffolding for the artists engaged to copy the frescoes on the back wall of the verandah. The copying work being over the mound was cleared off in the year under report.

12. Cave No. 3 also was completely freed from the enormous mass of debris choking its interior and particularly its entrance.

13. Caves Nos. 2, 3, 4 and 5, the only caves in this group that are worthy or capable of preservation, have now been freed from practically all the debris but caves Nos. 4 and 5, especially the former which is also the most interesting in the series, are immediately in need of masonry supports to prop up their overhanging ceilings and this work awaits being undertaken in the coming season.

14. Only a small portion of the vast expanse of frescoes that originally adorned the walls of the spacious verandah of caves Nos 4 and 5 is now surviving and this too is in a very precarious condition being badly exposed to weather, the protecting roof of the verandah having fallen away. And moreover being quite an out-of-the-way place, Bagh attracts but few visitors. Hence the question of removing the frescoes bodily and exhibiting them suitably at a central place like Gwalior with the double object of securing the valuable relics against total destruction and of making them easily accessible to visitors was under consideration.

15. Expert advice on this point was sought from Sir John Marshall, the Director-General of Archæology in India, who very kindly took the trouble to examine the frescoes on the spot in February and advised that considering the condition of the paintings their removal would be both unjustifiable and impracticable. The idea of removing the frescoes has therefore been finally abandoned and it has been decided to carry out Sir John's recommend-

ations to erect a verandah of a simple design of timber and steel roofed over with suitable tiles, in front of the frescoes to protect them *in situ* from rain and dust.

16. **Chanderi.**—The monuments conserved at this place during the year of report are: (a) Katighati, (b) the Delhi gate, (c) Shahzadika Roza, (d) Madarsa tomb, (e) Battisi Baodi and some minor domes.

17. (a) Katighati is the name of a pass cut through a hill where it is crossed by the old road leading from Chanderi towards the South. In the middle of the cutting a screen of rock is carved in the form of a pointed archway which on its northern face is flanked on either side by a tapering tower or bastion also hewn in the living rock. In the eastern wall of the cutting a flight of steps is carved out for getting up to the roof over the gate. The gateway bears an inscription in Sanskrit as well as in Persian recording that it was made by Jimankhan, son of Sherkhan in Samvat 1547 (= A. C. 1490) during the reign of Ghias Shah of Malwa.

18. The gateway was over-grown with jungle including five or six rather big trees which had thrust their roots into the crevices of the rock and were threatening to split it. The jungle was cleared away, the trees cut off and their roots extracted. Heaps of debris blocked the site of the road on both sides all along the cutting. These were dug up and thrown away. Structural parapet walls and a room of rubble masonry built in later times on the top of the rock-cut gateway were in a dilapidated condition. A large mass of debris consisting of rubble mixed with earth, which came out of these ruins, formed an unnecessary weight on the top of the rock and was a constant source of trouble as it provided a favourable breeding ground to small vegetation and large trees. The debris was therefore cleared off. The top of the gateway was made proof against rain water entering the crevices or percolating in the rock, by laying a coat of stone concrete in lime over it. The parapet walls were restored to an average height of 2 feet above the level of the concrete roof. There was no means to ascertain in what manner the top line of the walls had originally been finished. The tops of walls were therefore left uneven so as to impart them an unfinished appearance. Stone spouts were provided to throw off the rain water on the roof clear of the gateway.

19. (b) Delhi Darwaza is the principal gate in the city wall of Chanderi and faces the north. The gateway is flanked by a circular bastion on either side. It bears a Persian inscription stating that it was erected in A. H. 814 (= A. C. 1411). It is thus one of the oldest monuments at this place.

20. It was freed from small jungle. Two small banyan trees growing on it were rooted out. The debris of a rubble hut put up on the top of the gate in later times to serve, it is said, as quarters for a police guard, was picked up and thrown away as it was causing a dangerous burden on the ceiling slabs of the gateway and was also serving as a breeding ground for vegetation and trees. A ceiling slab which had cracked was replaced by a new one.

21. (c) Shahzadika Roza—It is a small but fine specimen of a tomb. It consists of a single domed chamber standing on a high plinth. The loss of dome has deprived it of half its beauty but nevertheless its ornamental

features, namely, the cornices, the lines of eaves supported on wavy brackets, and the top course of decorative battlements on the exterior, as well as the pointed arches, the rosettes and the ornamented base of the dome in the interior make it a monument well worth preservation.

22. It was freed from grass and jungle of trees, small and large, with which it was enveloped both inside and outside. The inside of the chamber was full of debris fallen from the ruins of the dome above. It was cleared off, so as to expose the original lime floor. The grave stones which had got displaced were reset properly. The heaps of debris and rubbish in which the plinth was half buried were dug out and dressed up into a regular platform. As the interior view of the tomb is interesting, steps were provided leading to the entrance door at the top of the high plinth.

23. (d) Madarsa Tomb—This monument had been partially conserved two years ago. But the ground surrounding the monument sloped sharply on one side which helped rain water to wash away and undermine the foundations of its plinth. Partly to prevent this damage, partly to cover up the unsightly debris and thus to impart the tomb a neat and tidy appearance, an earth platform extending up to a width of 10 feet from the sides of the plinth, with a level top and regular slopes was put up. Boundary pillars enclosing a square area 25 feet all round the monument were set up and the intervening space cleared and tidied up. A line of jungle 10 feet wide was cut up and cleared away in order to make the monument visible and easily accessible from the adjoining shikar road which is motorable.

24. (e) Battisi Baodi—This is the largest and perhaps the most remarkable of all the baodis which are proverbially numerous at Chanderi. It is a square tank 60 feet each way and sinks by four stages or storeys. Besides the principal stairway which is in the south side there are two flights of steps in each of the four sides of each of the four storeys thus making the number of stairs thirty-two from which apparently the well takes its name. It is built of chisel dressed stone and is said to have originally stood in the midst of a beautiful park which perhaps justified the author of the inscription on the well, exclaiming 'if any one visits this place he will say "It is Heaven."' The inscription records that the well was built in A. H. 890 (= A. C. 1485) in the reign of Ghias Shah Khalji of Mandu.

25. The jungle growing on the masonry and within an area of 25 feet all round the well was cleared off. The rubble walls of a hut built in later times, stood in a dilapidated condition near the south-east corner of the well and disfigured its view. They were therefore dismantled and thrown away. The coping slabs on the top of the retaining walls of the well and the paving stones on the top of the platform in front of the principal stairs of the well which serves as a seat for visitors had sunk in places. They were raised up and properly reset.

26. Boundary stone pillars were set up enclosing an area of 25 feet all round the well including the main stairs and the platform which projects on the south side of the well. A fair weather road was laid out to connect the well with the shikar road between Chanderi and Budhi Chanderi and a notice board was erected at the junction to call attention of passers by.

27. (f) Minor Monuments—Besides these some minor monuments at Chanderi also received attention. For instance, the simple domed tomb known as Akol-ki-Bag-ka-Gumbaz was freed from jungle and petty repairs done to its compound wall. Another small tomb named Badaiyon-ka-Gumbaz also was freed from jungle and the masonry of its plinth wherever damaged was made good. Further the isolated but handsome gateway called Badal Mahal Darwaza which stood in the midst of dense jungle was liberated from it.

28. **Budhi Chanderi.**—The ruins of the old or pre-Muhammadan Chanderi which appears to have been deserted soon after the Muhammadan conquest of that tract of country in favour of the present site of Chanderi are now enveloped in large and thick jungle and have become a favourite haunt of wild beasts. The town is popularly believed to have been the capital of the Chedi king Sisupala who was the rival of Sri Krishna, but the existing vestiges of temples and houses do not carry the antiquity of the place beyond the 9th century A. C. The town possessed quite a number of temples in three different groups all of which with two solitary exceptions are now reduced to mere heaps of debris. The temples are predominantly of the Digambara Jaina sect. Judging from the style of architecture and sculpture they range between the 9th and 11th centuries. The conservation of the temples except perhaps of one or two is out of question. But the ruins contain many sculptures of the Jaina Tirthankaras, which, both from the artistic and iconographic point of view, are of great interest and hence too good to be left to themselves. It is therefore proposed to pick these up from the debris in which most of them lie buried and arrange them into groups near the temple to which they originally belonged. As a preliminary measure the most important group of the ruins which lies at the south-east corner of the site of the town was cleared of jungle to facilitate close examination of the sculptures and carvings. The open courtyard of one of the two temples which are standing was freed from jungle and debris with which it was choked and some beautiful sculptures of Tirthankaras exposed in the debris or lying scattered on the site were picked up and arranged in order against the wall of the court, to form a sort of open air museum. It is proposed to pursue this same process with regard to other important temples in this group. This work will be taken up as soon as convenient.

29. **Udaypur.**—It was stated in the last year's report that the famous Nilakanthesvar temple had been taken in hand for conservation and the repairs to the temple proper and the mosque near it had been mostly carried out. It was further stated that a proposal to acquire the *kachcha* houses which have trespassed into the original spacious compound of the temple and thus disfigured its appearance was under consideration. The proposal having been sanctioned proceedings were instituted to acquire the houses by compensating the owners under *Qanun Husul Arazi* (The Land Acquisition Act). The acquisition has now been effected and the work of throwing away rubbish and debris from the open areas and exposing the original pavement floor of the compound is in progress. The work of dismantling the houses themselves is postponed till after the rainy season.

30. **Narwar.**—Within the walls of the hill fort of Narwar stand the ruins of an extensive town of the Rajput period not more than half a dozen houses in which are now inhabited. It is well known that in pre-Muhammadian times Narwar teemed with Jaina and Hindu temples which were subsequently demolished by the order of Sikandar Lodi of Delhi. At present there is not a single pre-Muhammadian building on the fort except perhaps the large tank known as Makardhvaja Tal and the remains of a small medieval shrine near the Hawa Paur or Wind Gate, on the eastern road to the fort.

31. The eastern portion of the town on the fort was occupied by a group of *Mahals* or residential palaces of the ruling families, which are separated from the rest of the town, by means of a tall enclosure wall. These appear to have been built by the later Kachhawaha (or may be by Tomara) chiefs and are thus not more than 300 years old. The style of architecture is Rajput. The pillars are fluted and tapering upwards. The arches are of multifoil designs. The ceilings and roofs are all flat and in places the walls and ceilings show remnants of paintings in which men and women in Rajput costume can be clearly traced. The buildings are mostly two-storeyed. There are a series of enclosures forming separate units containing audience halls, baths, garden pavilions, harems with screened windows and galleries and quite a number of swing-posts. One of these *Mahals* called Kachehri Mahal which possesses some fine ornamental work of plaster inlaid with glass, and part of which is set on the eastern verge of the fort, thus commanding a view of the valley of the Sindh river which after rounding the fort-hill flows in the eastern direction, appealed to the tasteful fancy of His late Highness who ordered that the whole of the Mahal should be cleared up generally and the eastern part of it should be thoroughly repaired and converted into a rest-house.

32. This work having been entrusted to this Department and a special grant sanctioned for this purpose, the necessary repairs are being carried out, due care being taken to preserve the original design of the general plan and the decorations as far as possible. Along with this the following works were carried out with regard to other old buildings of interest on the fort.

33. The approach-road was improved by making a fair weather road from the *Basar* to the foot of the hill, repairing the *Khwanja* of the old paved road, providing supplementary stairs of masonry steps along side that portion of the old road where it was too steep and had become slippery with the wearing away of its pavement, dismantling and re-building one of the big bastions which had fallen and blocked the road and providing a fair weather road from the top-most gate of the fort up to the Kachehri Mahal, dangerous portions of buildings on both sides of this road having been either dismantled, repaired or tidied up.

34. The other old palaces which are of considerable architectural interest being in an advanced condition of ruin and covered up with jungle had become inaccessible to visitors. A decent foot-path giving access to most of the more interesting buildings and objects was therefore laid out after cutting the strips of jungle and clearing away the heaps of debris which came in the

way and dismantling or repairing the portions of masonry which appeared to be dangerous to the safety of the visitors.

34. (a) The Ladau Bungalow which is comparatively a later building and is almost intact was thoroughly cleared of jungle and debris. The damaged portions of the retaining walls of its plinth were repaired and the fallen pieces of the *Jali* enclosure were reset.

35. (b) The building known as Chhip Mahal was similarly cleared. The chief object of interest about this Mahal and from which the latter takes its name is a large monolithic trough carved out in the form of a trefoil oval in a block of pink-coloured stone. It is popularly known as Chhip. It is locally believed to have been used as the receptacle of pounded saffron, a mark of which was put on the forehead of each Rajput soldier before he proceeded to the fighting line. It may have been used for this purpose or else as a tub for royal bath. The area round about the Chhip was completely cleared, damaged portions of the masonry and the terrace close by were repaired and a flight of steps was provided to get up to the spot in place of a slippery and sloping path over heaps of debris.

36. (c) The retaining walls of the old tank known as Makaradhvaja Tal were repaired wherever they had been damaged. In the bed of the tank there are several wells from one of which it is proposed to take water to the rest-house by means of a hand-pump and a line of pipes.

37. (d) The big mosque built by Sikandar Lodi was freed from jungle and debris.

38. (e) The compound of a tomb known as Madar Shah-ki-Dargah was cleared of rubbish and tidied up.

39. (f) Another monument conserved at Narwar during the year of report is the *Jait Khamba* or pillar of victory, an inscription on which records the genealogy of the Tomara kings of Gwalior and Narwar. This monolithic pillar is about 20 feet high above the ground and stands nearly two furlong east of the road from Narwar to Magroni at a distance of about $1\frac{1}{2}$ miles to the north-east of the town of Narwar. It appears that there was originally some sort of a platform round the base of the pillar. But nothing survived out of it except a few stray boulders. Owing to the absence of any protection the earth round the base of the column was being gradually washed away and the foundations were in danger of being undermined. To ensure the stability of the pillar therefore, a platform $10' \times 10' \times 3'$ of dry rubble masonry was put up round its base with steps in the east face, the top being paved with stone slabs laid in lime. From the top of the new platform one can conveniently examine the inscription which is only $5\frac{1}{2}$ feet high above the platform. It is further proposed to fix up a tablet on the platform giving a substance of the original inscription in English and Hindi.

40. **Mandasor.**—Another group of monuments selected for conservation during the year of report consists of the huge sculpture of Siva in the fort of Mandasor, the famous inscribed pillars of Yasodharman at Sondni about two miles to the south-east of Mandasor and the Torana pillar at Khilchipura about two miles south of Mandasor. A detailed reference to this work

however had better been reserved for the next year's Report, as only a nominal beginning has been made this year.

41. A list of monuments conserved is shown in Appendix B.

VI. Annual Upkeep and Maintenance.

42. Annual clearance and maintenance were attended to in the case of all the important groups of conserved monuments.

43. There was an unfortunate case of vandalism in the year of report. It related to the famous Koshak Mahal near Chanderi. The lower subordinates of the P. W. D. and the contractors who worked under them were the offenders.

44. The case was referred to the Administrative Officer, P. W. D., for necessary disciplinary action.

45. It is further proposed to appoint a caretaker to look after the monuments at Chanderi.

46. It is requested that the public will be good enough to treat these National Relics with the reverence they deserve.

VII. Exploration.

(a) Excavations.

47. Trial excavations were made in the year of report at Pawaya. Pawaya is situated at the confluence of the Sindh and the Parvati about 40 miles to the south-west of Gwalior. The site has been identified as the ancient town of Padmavati, one of the three capitals of the Nagas (for a detailed description of the site and its antiquities see my article on 'The Site of Padmavati' in the *Annual Report of the Archaeological Survey of India* for 1915-16, pp. 104-105).

48. Naga coins, and sculptures dating from the Sunga and Gupta period (100 to 500 A. C.) have been found here. The ground in the whole area is studded with brick bats, and brick wallings are met with under ground. Sir John Marshall, the Director-General of Archæology in India, visited the place in 1920 and agreed with me that it looked like a promising site for archæological excavations. As the history of the Nagas is still veiled in obscurity it is hoped that systematic excavations of Padmavati may illuminate that obscure period (3rd-4th centuries) of Indian History. The work however is an expensive one and with the limited funds at our disposal we have but to work little by little and wait patiently for the fulfilment of the expectations.

49. The spot selected for the trial excavations this year is a conspicuous artificial mound about half a mile towards the north, outside the site of the city proper. The mound measures nearly 200 feet by 200 feet by 30 feet (high). The area around was studded with brick bats. The palm capital of a stone pillar was discovered lying at its foot some years ago. There was therefore every indication that the mound contained in its womb the ruins of an ancient structure.

50. The work of excavations was carried on for about six weeks in all. An average of 100 coolies a day was employed. On opening the mound by means of radiating trenches on all the four sides, the retaining walls of a big

square platform were lighted upon. The position of the four sides of the platform having been defined, digging was concentrated on the east side where the approach steps or a gate was expected to exist. So far we have been able to clear up the four corners of the platform, the immediate neighbourhood of the east retaining wall, and small portions here and there of the other three retaining walls. The platform is a solid one. It is constructed of large bricks laid in clay mortar. The average size of bricks is 18" × 9" × 3". The platform rises in a number of stages, each stage being marked by an offset. Each side measures 140 feet long approximately. The existing height of the platform is 30 feet. So far no approach stairs or gateway has been discovered. Remnants have been found of a smaller platform also square on plan and superimposed upon the lower one. This latter platform is also solid and measures 56 feet each way. The exterior of this platform is decorated with a horizontal moulding at the base and ornamental vertical pilasters at regular intervals all in brick. It appears that the exterior of the building was further decorated with *terra cotta* figures and carvings, a number of which have been found in the diggings. None of these however was found *in situ*.

51. On the evidence so far disclosed it has not been possible to decide once for all the nature of the monument that we have come upon. The solidity and the dimensions of the platform point to its being a *stupa*. Instances of *stupas* with square plinths are not uncommon. But, on the other hand, no relics or sculptures distinctly Buddhist or Jaina have so far been found associated with this structure. A well sunk in the centre of the top of the platform and carried down right up to the ground level disclosed no trace of any kind of relics. Moreover, the few pieces of stone sculptures that have been unearthed in these excavations are all of a Brahmanical nature. For instance, fragments of a big lintel of a *Torana* gateway have been found, the subjects sculptured on which are all from Brahmanical mythology, namely, (1) the scene of Bali's sacrifice and Vishnu taking the three strides, (2) Karttikeya, (3) the scene of the churning of the ocean, etc. The subjects on the carved decorative bricks are all secular and afford no clue to distinguish the sectarian character of the monument. It may be that we have after all come upon a Brahmanical temple perched on the top of a huge platform. If this surmise is correct,—further excavations alone will show if it is so—there is no hope of finding the temple itself. It has already disappeared. There is however some hope of finding the remnants of its decorations, a gateway or gateways which gave access to the place and last but not least a stone column probably recording the history of this monument in an inscription. That one or more gateways and the pillar originally existed here is evident from the big piece of carved stone lintel unearthed in the excavations and from the stone palm capital which was found lying on the site some years ago.

52. Strangely enough not a single coin was found in the diggings although a number of them are found on the site of the city proper above the surface of the ruins, after rains. The age of the building discovered can, however, be determined with some certainty. It cannot be later than the early Gupta period, as the style of all the stone sculptures and of carvings on bricks unearthed point distinctly to that period.

53. A descriptive list of all the more important antiquities unearthed in these diggings is given in Appendix C.

54. Fuller details of the excavations must be reserved until the work makes further progress in subsequent years.

(b) **Listing.**

55. In the year of report 33 monuments comprising temples, groups of rock-cut sculptures, mahals, mosques, tombs, old wells, sati stones, etc. situated at 11 different places were listed. A list of these appears in Appendix D. The following is a brief description of the monuments.

56. **Chanderi.**—About a mile to the north-east of the town of Chanderi are the ruins of a large enclosure with two gateways, one in the centre of its east wall and the other in the centre of the north wall. The eastern gateway which is the better preserved of the two is a double arch built one over the other. Above the inner arch which forms the entrance is an arched window with projecting brackets which supported a balcony. The gateway is flanked on either side by a tall round *minar* the upper portion of which has fallen away. The northern gate was similar in design but is in a worse state of disrepair though its *minars* have still preserved their tops. The enclosure wall is of rubble and is now mostly fallen. The area enclosed is about 200 feet $\times$ 200 feet. There are no traces of buildings inside and it is doubtful what purpose it was intended to serve. People call it *Mehman Sarai* or guest-house. If the tradition is correct probably tents were pitched inside the enclosure to accommodate the guests. It is curious that both the gates of this enclosure face away from the town.

57. A short distance to the north of this enclosure is a small *minar* and a square well called Bandar Baodi or Monkey well. Why it is so-called is not known.

58. Nearly a furlong further east is a mosque and a square Baodi in a grove known as Qazi's Bag. The mosque bears a Persian inscription recording its construction in the reign of Aurangzeb in A. H. 1113 = A. C. 1701.

59. A little further is a group of about a dozen small *maqbaras* or tombs only two of which have retained their domes. Interspersed in the tombs are three mosques. One of the mosques and one of the tombs bear inscriptions showing that they are works of the reign of Aurangzeb. Some of these tombs possess finely perforated stone screens which form the side-walls of their rooms.

60. Still further east about three furlongs on the other side of the Singhpur Road is a square step well called Chandai Baodi. It sinks in stages two of which were visible above water at the time of my visit. But I was told there were two more stages concealed under water. An ornamental horizontal band demarcates the highest storey from the one next below. Two stairs are provided in each face of every stage. At the top the well measures 54' $\times$ 54'. In the second storey from above there is a niche in each of its three sides southern, eastern and western. The southern niche is empty. The eastern niche is occupied by a Sanskrit inscription and the western niche by a Persian inscription probably a translation of the former. The inscription

slabs are badly worn out by water and weather and the lower portions of the epigraphs are altogether lost. From the salutation to and praise of the *Jinas* in the opening lines of the Sanskrit record it would appear that the well is the work of a Jaina donor.

61. Chetan Baodi is a circular step well situated in the north-east portion of the town. Its diameter is 29'6". The construction of steps in the lower half portion of the well is peculiar. They are set obliquely instead of being at right angles to the wall.

62. The Jaina temple popularly known as Chaubisi in the town of Chanderi is remarkable for the life-size idols in Jaipur marble of all the 24 (*Chaubis*) *Tirthamkaras* which are enshrined there, each in a cell crowned with a conical spire and arranged round a rectangular courtyard. Every idol is made in accordance with the specification as to *varna* (colour), *lanchhana* (symbol), etc., given in old works on Jaina iconography. The temple is however not very old being built in V. S. 1893 = 1836 A. C. by Hirde Sahai, a well-wisher (*Subha Chintaka*) of Mardan Singh, a Bundela king of Chanderi. Outside the quadrangle is a bigger shrine-room covered with a hemispherical dome sheltering a number of promiscuous images of *Tirthamkaras*. This is a few years older than the Chaubisi temple being constructed in V. S. 1857 or A. C. 1800.

63. There is another Jaina temple in the town which possesses some old images, namely, an image of Parsvanatha, dated V. S. 1252, a sculpture of goddess Padmavati, dated in V.S. 1291, and another idol of a *Tirthamkara* dated V. S. 1316.

64. Another temple listed in the year at the same place is a small domed shrine of Siva situated near what is known as Dariba Baodi, a short distance to the east of Paramesvari Tal. The shrine bears on the lintel of its door an interesting inscription in pure Sanskrit poetry (*Kavya* style) recording that it was constructed by Sri Manasimha, one of the Bundela kings, in V. S. 1784. The temple is called Manasimhesvara after the name of its founder.

65. Other monuments noticed at Chanderi are the two mosques known as Hatpura-ki-Masjid and Mirza-ki-Masjid both with inscriptions, two tombs of Christian soldiers in the army led by J. B. Filose as the tablets on them are dated in A. C. 1816 and 1819, respectively, and a rectangular masonry-built tank named Visurkund or Vishnukund in the neighbourhood of another similar tank named Harakund.

66. **Singhpur.**—Three miles to the north-east of Chanderi stands one of the *Mahals* built by Bundela Rajas of Chanderi. It is picturesquely situated in the midst of charming mountain scenery overlooking a lake. But for its pleasant site it is in no way remarkable. It has been repaired and converted into a shooting box or rest-house by the order of the late Maharaja Scindia.

67. **Khanpura.**—Khanpura is a village about 4 miles to the east of Chanderi. On the eastern outskirts of the village stand a few Sati stones one of which bears an inscription, dated V. S. 1545 = A. C. 1488.

68. **Gurila-ka-Pahad.**—About 8 miles to the south-east of Chanderi is the hill known as Gurila-ka-Pahad. On the top of the hill which is rather difficult of access are the ruins of two temples of the Digambara Jaina sect standing

in an enclosure of rough masonry. One of these consists of a shrine room and an entrance-porch facing west. On the shrine is a hemispherical dome of which the rubble frame is now exposed its plaster facing having peeled off. Enshrined is a big image of Santinatha 11' 9" tall but broken in twain across the neck.

69. Facing this is another temple consisting of an oblong shrine room with three entrance doors and a pillared verandah in front. The temple is 20' long and 17' 3" wide externally and has a flat roof. There are in all 26 images of Jaina *Tirthankaras* (some standing, others seated) leaning against the three walls of the shrine. The central image is that of Adinatha. None of the other images bears a *lanchhana* or distinctive symbol by which it can be identified.

70. Two lines of an obliterated inscription on a wall of the temple—probably a pilgrim's record—is dated in V. S. 1307. The temple therefore cannot be later than this date.

71. **Naderi.**—At the foot of this hill is the village called Naderi. It possesses a number of old relics. The earliest is a Sati memorial not less than five or six centuries old. The sculpture on it shows that it is the memorial of a man killed by a tiger, and his wife who cremated herself on his funeral pyre.

72. Another inscribed Sati pillar near a well called Dhimara is dated in V. S. 1545, which records that the Sati was a blacksmith's wife. This record gives the old name of the villages as Guler from which evidently the adjoining hill has derived its name Gurila-ka-Pahad by an interchange of letters. On the western extrimity of the village is a ruined Jaina temple which itself appears to have been built out of materials partly taken from older Hindu temples, as sculptures representing the Dwarf and the Rama incarnations of Vishnu are seen in a wall and on a pillar, respectively.

73. Outside the village is a large step well known as *Ajican Baodi* which bears in a niche a Sanskrit inscription recording its construction in V. S. 1577 (= A. C. 1520) in the reign of Mahmud Khilji of Malwa. Near this is another round well with a flight of steps reaching down to water.

74. **Mohanpur.**—About 6 miles to the north of Chanderi on the way to Budhi Chanderi is the village of Mohanpur. In this village is a comparatively modern but ruined temple of Nrisimha in which a few carved pillars and a door frame of mediæval temples probably brought from the ruins of Budhi Chanderi have been used. In the middle of the village is a small open enclosure in which some fragments of old Jain sculptures have been stored. Outside the village is a modern Jaina temple called Chaityalaya where an old image of a *Tirthankara* is enshrined.

75. **Budhi Chanderi.**—A fresh monument noticed at Budhi Chanderi is an inscribed Sati stone, dated in V. S. 1545 (= A. C. 1488) and giving the name of the place as Nasirabad, as Budhi Chanderi appears to have been named by the Muhammadan conquerors.

76. **Lakhari.**—Village of Lakhari is 5 miles north-west of Budhi Chanderi. It is surrounded on all sides by old relics.

77. On the west of the village are two small Saiva shrines standing in a row facing the east, on a common plinth and having a pillared porch in

front of each. The side walls of the shrine consist of single slabs. The door frame of one shrine is still standing and bears on its lintel the images of Brahma, Siva, Vishnu and *Navagrahas* and a Sanskrit inscription, dated V. S. 1000. The door frame of the other has fallen down and on the back of one of the loose door posts an image of Hanuman has been carved in relief in later times. Close to these shrines are two rectangular wells built of large blocks of stone which appear to be contemporary with the shrines. The bigger of the two wells measures 16' × 16'.

78. Nearly a furlong to the east of the village is an old temple locally known as *madh* facing the north. It consists of a shrine room 6' 3" × 7' 1" and a *Sabha Mandapa* 23' 6" × 16' 3" in front of it. Both the shrine room and the hall are covered with a flat roof supported on pillars and pilasters. The enshrined idol is rather unusual. It is a group of Brahma, Vishnu and Siva carved in relief on a stone slab. The central place is occupied by Siva flanked by Brahma on one side and Vishnu on the other. It may be that the slab originally formed the lintel of a door.

79. The temple appears to be seven or eight centuries old but has been repaired in later times.

80. About half way between this temple and the village is the site of an old Jaina temple of which the only remnants are two or three mutilated idols and a few architectural pieces.

81. A loose inscription slab, dated in V. S. 1124, was found in a well close by. This was removed to the Museum (see Appendix E. No. 22).

82. An isolated hill called *Vindhyavasini Tekri* to the north of the village is crowned with a modern rubble hut in which a small old idol of the goddess Mahishamardini is enshrined.

83. **Bithla.**—The village of Bithla lies about 5 miles to the south-west of Budhi Chanderi. Some two furlongs to the north-west of the village are a number of Jaina temples. Only one of these is standing at present, but there were at least four more. These latter are now fallen into heaps of ruins. The temple which is still standing faces roughly the west. It consists of a shrine room with a projecting entrance porch, the whole measuring externally 33' × 16'. The door frame is carved in the usual way. On the lintel are sculptured three *Tirthamkaras* in a row the middle one being seated and the other two standing. In the back-ground are small figures of the *Navagrahas*. Over the lintel is a frieze in the centre of which is an image of a seated four-armed goddess probably Padmavati with a figure of a seated *Tirthamkara* at either end. In the back-ground are small figures of standing *Tirthamkaras*. Enshrined against the back wall of the cells is a big standing image of a *Tirthamkara* whose head is half broken. There are five other small sculptures of *Tirthamkaras* in the shrine room but the feet and pedestals of one and all having been buried in the debris their *lanchhanas* or distinctive symbols, if any, are not visible. It was not possible to expose these and identify the images, during my short visit. Part of the back-wall of the shrine and the *Sikhara* have fallen away. The exterior of the shrine shows the usual ribs and offsets but they are plain, *i. e.*, not decorated with sculpture.

84. In the ruins of the attendant temples referred to above are seen carved pillars, door jambs, lintels, roof-slabs and a number of damaged sculptures of *Tirthankaras* among which two could be identified as Sambhavanatha with the symbol of a horse and Munisuvrata with the *lanchhana* of a tortoise respectively.

85. Judging from the style the temples may be assigned to the 12th century approximately.

86. **Rakhetra or Gadhelna.**—Within the limits of the village Rakhetra about 2 miles to the south-east of Bithla, carved in the western face of a hill overlooking the Orr river is a series of rock-cut sculptures.

87. The biggest sculpture in the group is the seated image of the Jaina *Tirthankara* Adinatha popularly known as Bhaiyadant or Bhimasena. The height of the image is 10' 6" and the width at the seat is 7' 6." The head dress is somewhat uncommon for a Jaina sculpture being in the form of *Jata* or matted hair. The head is flanked on either side by an elephant which is unfinished. On the right side of the bust of the sculpture is an image of the goddess Padmavati and on the left is that of the goddess Chakresvari. On the seat which is in the form of a mattress is a small figure of a bull, the distinctive symbol of Adinatha. The seat also bears an inscription, dated in V. S. 1675. On the pedestal below the seat is carved a *Dharma-Chakra* or the wheel of the law between two scenes of a lion fighting with an elephant.

88. At the point where this sculpture is carved, the face of the hill is chiselled into a right angle. The sculpture of Adinatha described above is carved on one of the arms of the right angle which faces the south. On the other arm which faces the west, is carved a small niche crowned with a spire in outline enclosing a pair of foot-prints of Sri Visalaraja as is recorded in an inscription over the niche, dated in V. S. 1555. The back wall of the niche is decorated with lotuses carved in relief and a figure of *Svastika* is carved in the floor on either side of the foot-prints.

89. In front of these sculptures is a rough rubble platform. Adjoining the platform is a small plain doorway leading into a cavern which is a natural one, to all appearances. For want of time this cavern was left over for a search at some other time.

90. Proceeding southwards beyond the cavern along the facade of the hill we come to a small figure of seated Ganesa carved in the rock. At a distance of 5 feet further is a four-armed figure of Parvati seated on a couching lion. The head is crowned with *Jata* and has a lotus halo behind it. The ears carry large rings. Three of the hands hold a sword, a shield and a trident and the fourth is folded in the form of *Dharmachakramudra*.

91. Some 10 feet further south, in the same face of the hill, are three niches in a row each measuring 2' 2" × 1' 7½" approximately. The central niche contains a twelve-armed figure of Siva dancing, surrounded by his attendants Nandi and others. In the niche on the right of Siva is Brahma and in that on the left is Vishnu manifesting himself in the Boar incarnation.

92. On the other side of the big sculpture of Adinatha, *i. e.*, towards the north, one comes across two small niches carved in the rock containing unfinished groups of Hara-Gauri. Further on, there are traces of a similar

group. Still further north in the same facade, are two niches each sheltering a group of Siva and Parvati with their vehicles the bull and the lion under them. The top corners of both the niches are occupied by figures of Brahma and Vishnu. Over the principal images in one niche are two flying figures supporting a crown and in the other niche is a small group of dancing Siva and his attendants (*Tandava*). In the space between the two niches is a group of a god and goddess unfinished and a small but finished figure of Vishnu carved in the rock.

93. Further northwards is a tablet in the rock bearing a Sanskrit inscription in six lines dated in V. S. 999 and 1000 (see Appendix E. No. 32). Still further again are two niches each sheltering a group of Hara-Gauri and having a small structural porch in front of it.

94. A few carved pillars, brackets and pedestals are lying scattered on the ground in the neighbourhood attesting to the existence here of a structural shrine or shrines at one time.

95. The Hindu sculptures in this locality would appear to be contemporary with the inscription noted above, *i. e.*, of about the middle of the 10th century A. C. While the Jaina sculptures are more than five centuries later. The neighbouring hill-side has collapsed into a heap of debris which tempts one to surmise that there were perhaps some rock-cut caves in the locality.

96. The view of the collapsed hill-side with the river Orr flowing at its foot is strikingly similar to that of the excavated hill overlooking the Bagh river with this difference, however, that here is a dense and green jungle and an abundant stream of water while the landscape at Bagh is rather rugged.

VIII. Epigraphy.

97. Appendix No. E. shows an analysis of inscriptions noticed in the year of report, and the numbers of inscriptions in this section refer to this Appendix.

98. Forty-eight inscriptions were copied or noticed during the year under report. Of these 28 are in Sanskrit or Hindi, 19 in Arabic or Persian and one in French. Classified according to the ruling dynasties two of these refer to early Hindu Kings, two to the Pathan kings of Delhi, seven to the Sultans of Malwa, six to the Mughal Emperors of Delhi, one to the Tomara Rajput dynasty of Gwalior and Narwar, one to the later Kachhwahas of Narwar, two to the Bundela kings of Chanderi and to the Scindias of Gwalior, while the rest mention no king. They were discovered variously at Budhi Chanderi, Chanderi, Khanpur, Lakhari, Rakhetra and Singhpur (in District Esagarh), Narwar Fort and town (District Narwar) and Ujjain city. Out of these Nos. 22 and 35 being loose slabs have been removed to the Museum and number 46 which came from the Mochiwada gate at Ujjain dismantled by the Town Improvement Trust is preserved in the Madhava College, Ujjain.

99. Among the Sanskrit inscriptions No. 32 is an important one. It is incised in the rock on the right bank of the river Orr within the limits of the village Rakhetra, not far from the old site of Chanderi. It is dated in V. S. 999 and again in V. S. 1000. It has not been satisfactorily interpreted so far but apparently it refers to the construction of some sort of water works connected with the Orr river perhaps at a cost of 95 or 96 crores of coins

by Vinayakapaladeva who was probably the same as his name-sake mentioned in the Chandela inscription at Khajuraho, dated V. S. 1011 (*Epigraphia Indica*, Volume I, pp. 124 ff.). This place appears to have been included in the then Chandela kingdom. A king of Gopagiri (Gwalior) whose name however is not given is also mentioned. He was connected with these works in some way or other.

100. An inscription, dated in V. S. 1124, found at Lakhari mentions a Maharajadhiraja Abhayadeva and his son, prince Chandraditya but neither of these is known so far from other sources.

101. Two fragments of stone found at Ujjain appear to belong to a very large Sanskrit inscription of about the 10th to 11th centuries, extending over several hundreds of verses, written in the high flown *kavya* style. Unfortunately, however, the fragments discovered are too small to give us any idea of the purport of the inscription.

102. Of Musalman inscriptions No. 10 which is dated in A. H. 711 (=1311 A. C.) is of importance, being the earliest Musalman inscription so far discovered at Chanderi. Allauddin Khilji invaded Chanderi in A. C. 1304 and the inscription under reference records the construction of a mosque here only seven years after this invasion.

IX. Numismatics.

103. One thousand four hundred and seven coins were examined in the year of report. Of these five were of gold, 101 of silver and 1,301 of copper. All these coins with the exception of 95 silver and 229 copper coins which were received from the State Museum as duplicates, came from treasure-trove finds. The gold coins were found at Sehora (District Esagarh) and the rest came from Dungarpur (District Narwar), and Shajapur (District Shajapur).

104. Out of these, all the five pieces of gold, 53 of silver and 63 of copper or, 121 coins in all, have been acquired for the Archaeological Museum.

105. Most important of these acquired coins are the five gold pieces, which belong to Chandragupta II of the Gupta dynasty (A.C. 375-413) and are of the type represented in the *Indian Museum Catalogue* plate XV, No. 12.

Of the silver coins 2 are of Shahjahan I (A. H. 1061) of Delhi mint, 10 belong to later Mughals up to Shah Alam II and range in date between A. H. 1207 and 1281, representing Benares and Bhuj mints.

106. The rest of the silver and some of the copper coins are from duplicates in the State Museum and have been acquired for our cabinet. Most of these belong to Scindia Rulers of Gwalior, European powers including Colonies and represent English, French, Italian, Portuguese, Austrian, and American (U. S. A.) currency. The copper coins belong to later Mughals or rather to Indian States who were subordinate to them including Orchha, Bhopal, Kota, Bundi, Jaipur and Dhar (*vide* Appendix No. F.).

X. Archaeological Museum.

107. Two stone inscriptions, one Sanskrit and the other Persian Nos. 22 and 35 of Appendix No. E, eight stone sculptures, nineteen old paintings, five gold, fifty-three silver and sixty-three copper coins and about eighty minor antiquities mostly brick carvings unearthed in the excavations at

Pawaya (old Padmavati) were added to the Museum in the year under report, and are detailed in Appendix No. C.

108. One sculpture in black (slate) stone representing Hara Gauri seated on their respective *vahanas* was purchased from outside the State. The rest were acquired from different parts of the State. All of them belong to the mediæval period. The most conspicuous among these are the huge sculptures of Siva slaying Gajasura, and his Sakti (Parvati) brought from Gyaraspur. The specimen of Matsya or Fish incarnation acquired in the year of report completes the series of the ten incarnations of Vishnu in our Museum.

109. All the nineteen miniature paintings were purchased locally. They represent the Mughal and Rajput Schools.

110. Among numismatic acquisitions, the five gold pieces of Chandragupta II are particularly noteworthy.

111. The Museum continues to be popular and attractive. 840 names have been signed in the Visitors' Book this year though the actual number of visitors must have been far greater. The number of European and American visitors exceeded 123. The addresses of Indian visitors represent all the provinces of British India and most Indian States. Among the distinguished visitors of the year may be mentioned Dr. Sten Konow, Dr. J. H. Cousins, Dr. A. K. Coomarswamy, Prof. Daruwala of Rajaram College, and Prof. A. Sen and historical party of Muzaffarpur (Behar) College.

XI. Visitors to Ancient Monuments.

112. The Buddhist rock-cut caves at Bagh (District Amjhera) are gradually emerging out of their obscurity and attracting more and more the attention of Indologists and sight-seers. With the publication of the monograph on these caves which is being carried through the press by the India Society of London in co-operation with this Department, the interest about this important group of caves is sure to be roused and it is expected that large numbers of visitors will hail not only from distant places in India but from all parts of the world, in spite of the fact that the caves are situated rather in an out-of-the-way place. But if we want to encourage travellers to visit these interesting relics of the past it is necessary that a branch road about three miles in length should be constructed to connect the caves with the Sardarpur-Kukshi Road and a small rest house be built close to the caves.

113. Sir John Marshall, the Director-General of Archæology in India, and Dr. J. H. Cousins, a well-known poet and art-critic, visited the caves in the year under report. The caves were also visited by a number of other visitors among whom about ten were Europeans who have recorded remarks of appreciations of what the Darbar have been doing to preserve and improve the condition of the caves. A few extracts from the remarks by the more distinguished visitors to these caves are quoted below :—

- (1) Remarks Sir John Marshall, the Director-General of Archæology in India : "India and all interested in Indian Art owe a deal of debt to His Highness the Maharaja for all that is being done for the preservation of these remains."

- (2) Writes Dr. J. H. Cousins: "This is one of the most important places in the history of Indian culture. Unfortunately time and human ignorance had gone too far in destruction before the Archæological Department took in hand the preservation of the excavations. It is to be hoped that their labours (so wisely and enthusiastically guided by Mr. M. B. Garde) may result in the passing on to posterity of these priceless remnants of India's golden age in painting and architecture."
- (3) Says A. Abraham of Jobat, C.I.: "Most interesting. Just another confirmation of India's wonderful past, and inspiration to those who live in the present. It is said that these places have not been preserved although they are now being kept in at least a clean condition."

The Surwaya monuments also attracted a fair number of visitors both Indian and European from Shivpuri and Jhansi.

XII. Publication and Contribution.

114. (a) A resumé of the exploration and conservation work done in the State in Samvat 1980 (year 1923-24) was contributed to All-India Archæological Survey Report.

(b) An illustrated article on Chanderi was contributed to the Birthday Special Number of the "Jayaji Pratap."

(c) An illustrated Guide to Chanderi is under preparation.

(d) In response to the demand of several non-English-knowing visitors to the Archæological Museum who saw there the English Edition of the Gwalior Fort Album, a Hindi Edition of the book was published and made available for sale in the year under report.

(e) A monograph on the Buddhist Caves at Bagh and on their fresco paintings in particular is in the press. In order to ensure the best possible printing of the colour reproductions of the frescoes the printing has been entrusted to the India Society of London who are authorised to publish the volume as one of their series on behalf of the Darbar. Such distinguished *savants* as Sir John Marshall, Dr. J. Ph. Vogel, Mr. Lawrence Binyon, Mr. E. B. Havell and others are among the contributors to the volume.

XIII. Photography.

115. Two hundred and forty-nine photographic negatives and seventy-four lantern slides were prepared in the year under report (see Appendix No. H and I.).

XIV. Office Library.

116. One hundred and one volumes on Archæology, Architecture, Art, History and allied subjects were added to the Office Library in the year under report (see Appendix No. J). Out of these sixty-eight were purchased and the rest were received as presents from the Government of India, Provincial Governments and Governments of Indian States to whom our thanks are due.

XV. Income and Expenditure.

117. The Budget of the Department is the same as it has been for the last six years. Statements of income and expenditure under different heads are set forth in Appendices Nos. K and L from which it will be seen that the year's expenditure was Rs. 46,192 which includes part of the special grant for conservation and repairs of certain monuments on the Narwar Fort. The income is Rs. 177 only.

XVI. Concluding Remarks.

118. It is impossible to close the report without referring to the greatest and the saddest event in the modern history of Gwalior, namely, the untimely demise of our late lamented ruler Maharaja Sir Madhav Rao Scindia, which occurred about the close of the year under report. The versatile Maharaja had his personal impress on the work of every one of the Departments and it was under his personal command that this Department carried out repairs to certain monuments in the Narwar Fort in the year of report. His guiding mind and hand are, alas, no more! but it may be confidently hoped that the Department will continue to make slow but sure progress as in the past, under the fostering care of the new Council of Regency constituted as it is of the same wise and experienced Councillors of the late Maharaja.

119. In conclusion I cannot but express my gratitude to Shrimant Sadashiv Rao Khase Sahib Pawar, the Home Member, for the unflinching courtesy and valuable guidance which he continued to extend to me in the discharge of the duties of my office.

M. B. GARDE,

Superintendent of Archæology,
Gwalior State.

APPENDIX NO. A.

Tour Diary of the Superintendent of Archaeology, Gwalior State, for Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

Date, Month and year.	Movements and Halts.
July 1924.	
26th-27th ...	Gwalior to Udaygiri <i>via</i> , Bhilsa.
28th-29th ...	Halt at Udaygiri.
30th ...	Udaygiri to Bhilsa.
31st ...	Bhilsa to Gwalior.
September 1924.	
14th ...	Gwalior to Shivpuri.
15th-17th ...	Halt at Shivpuri.
18th ...	Shivpuri to Gwalior.
22nd ...	Gwalior to Shivpuri.
23rd-24th ...	Halt at Shivpuri.
25th ...	Shivpuri to Gwalior.
November 1924.	
9th ...	Gwalior to Shivpuri.
10th ...	Halt at Shivpuri.
11th ...	Shivpuri to Narwar, Magroni and back to Shivpuri.
12th-14th ...	Halt at Shivpuri.
15th ...	Shivpuri to Surwaya.
16th ...	Surwaya to Shivpuri.
17th ...	Shivpuri to Gwalior.
December 1924.	
9th ...	Gwalior to Lalitpur.
10th ...	Lalitpur to Chanderi.
11th-16th ...	Halt at Chanderi.
17th ...	Chanderi to Naderi, Gurila-ka-Pahad, and back.
18th ...	Chanderi to Mohanpura.
19th ...	Mohanpura to Lidhora.
20th-21st ...	Halt at Lidhora.
22nd ...	Lidhora to Chanderi.
23rd-24th ...	Halt at Chanderi.
25th ...	Chanderi to Lalitpur.
26th ...	Lalitpur to Gwalior.
31st ...	Gwalior to Mhow.
January 1925.	
1st ...	Mhow to Bagh.
2nd ...	Halt at Bagh.
3rd-4th ...	Bagh to Bhilsa <i>via</i> , Mhow.
4th ...	Bhilsa to Udaygiri and back.
5th ...	Bhilsa to Kulhar, Badoh and back to Kulhar.
6th ...	Kulhar to Gwalior.
20th-21st ...	Gwalior to Mhow.
22nd ...	Halt at Mhow.
23rd-24th ...	Mhow to Gwalior.
February 1925.	
7th ...	Gwalior to Narwar Fort <i>via</i> , Satanwada.
8th ...	Halt at Narwar Fort.
9th ...	Narwar Fort to Gwalior <i>via</i> , Satanwada.
18th ...	Gwalior to Dabra.
19th ...	Dabra to Pawaya.
20th-27th ...	Halt at Pawaya for excavations.

Date, Month and year.	Movements and Halts.
28th ... March 1925.	Pawaya to Dabra and thence to Gwalior.
8th ...	Gwalior to Pawaya <i>via.</i> Dabra.
9th-13th ...	Halt at Pawaya.
14th ...	Pawaya to Gwalior <i>via.</i> , Dabra.
18th ...	Gwalior to Narwar <i>via.</i> Satanwada.
19th-21st ...	Halt at Narwar Fort.
22nd ...	Narwar to Gwalior <i>via.</i> Satanwada.
31st ...	Gwalior to Bhilsa.
April 1925	
1st ...	Halt at Bhilsa.
2nd-3rd ...	Bhilsa to Mhow.
3rd ...	Mhow to Bagh.
4th ...	Bagh to Bagh Caves.
5th-8th ...	Halt at Bagh Caves.
9th ...	Bagh to Tanda.
10th ...	Tanda to Sardarpur.
11th ...	Sardarpur to Mhow.
11th-12th ...	Mhow to Mandasor.
12th ...	Mandasor to Sonḍni and back.
13th-14th ...	Halt at Mandasor.
15th ...	Mandasor to Ujjain.
16th ...	Ujjain to Astronomical Observatory and back.
17th ...	Ujjain to Kaliadeh and back.
18th ...	Ujjain to Bhairongarh and back.
do. ...	Ujjain to Mungaoli <i>via.</i> Bina.
19th ...	Mungaoli to Chanderi.
20th-21st ...	Chanderi to Gwalior <i>via.</i> Mungaoli.
27th ...	Gwalior to Dabra.
28th ...	Dabra to Pawaya.
29th ...	Halt at Pawaya.
30th ...	Pawaya to Dabra.
May 1925.	
1st ...	Dabra to Gwalior.
6th ...	Gwalior to Narwar <i>via.</i> Satanwada.
7th-8th ...	Halt at Narwar.
9th ...	Narwar to Gwalior <i>via.</i> Satanwada.
11th ...	Gwalior to Dabra.
12th ...	Dabra to Pawaya.
13th-14th ...	Halt at Pawaya.
15th ...	Pawaya to Gwalior <i>via.</i> Dabra.
28th ...	Gwalior to Shivpuri.
29th-30th ...	Halt at Shivpuri.
31st ...	Shivpuri to Gwalior.
June 1925.	
20th ...	Gwalior to Narwar <i>via.</i> Satanwada.
21st-22nd ...	Halt at Narwar.
23rd ...	Narwar to Gwalior <i>via.</i> Satanwada.

Statement of expenditure incurred on monuments conserved during Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

Serial No.	Place.	Name of monument.	AMOUNT SANCTIONED.		Total. Rs. a. p.	AMOUNT SPENT.		Total. Rs. a. p.	REMARKS.
			Current year. Rs.	Last year. Rs. a. p.		Current year. Rs. a. p.	Last year. Rs. a. p.		
1	Chanderi	Katighati	825	...	825 0 0	739 15 0	...	739 15 0	
2	"	Delhi Gate	17	...	17 0 0	16 8 0	...	16 8 0	
3	"	Madarsa	144	...	144 0 0	136 5 0	...	136 5 0	
4	Sondni	Yasodharman's Pillars.	2,584	...	2,584 0 0	24 0 0	...	24 0 0	
5	Ranod	Khokhai	51	40 0 0	91 0 0	50 6 0	40 0 0	90 6 0	
6	Budhi Chanderi.	Jain Temple	16	...	16 0 0	15 8 6	...	15 8 6	
7	Bagh	Buddhist Caves	2,656	4 0 9	2,660 0 9	2,099 5 6	3 14 9	2,103 4 3	
8	Chanderi	Minor Monuments	441	...	441 0 0	428 7 6	...	428 7 6	
9	Mandasour	Gupta Image	698	...	698 0 0	28 0 0	...	28 0 0	
10	Bagh	Copying Frescoes	...	344 0 7	344 0 7	...	337 4 6	337 4 6	
11	Udaypur	Udayesvar Temple.	...	2,228 0 0	2,228 0 0	...	2,074 5 0	2,074 5 0	
12	Badoh	Jaina Temple	...	34 5 6	34 5 6	...	25 0 0	25 0 0	
13	"	Solah Khambhi	...	19 6 6	19 6 6	...	8 0 0	8 0 0	
14	"	Gadarimal Temple	...	75 6 6	75 6 6	...	62 8 0	62 8 0	
15	Bhilsa	Gumbaz-ka-Maqbari.	...	6 0 0	6 0 0	...	6 0 0	6 0 0	
16	"	Bijamandal Mosque.	...	5 7 6	5 7 6	...	5 7 6	5 7 6	
17	Ujjain	Observatory	...	7,000 0 0	7,000 0 0	...	6,568 10 0	6,568 10 0	Special grant.
18	Narwar	Fort Narwar	30,732	...	30,732 0 0	16,824 13 6	...	16,824 13 6	
19	"	Minor Monuments	142	...	142 0 0	39 10 3	...	39 10 3	
	TOTAL	...	38,306	9,756 11 4	48,062 11 4	20,402 15 3	9,131 1 9	29,544 1 0	

APPENDIX No. C.

LIST OF SELECTED ANTIQUITIES UNEARTHED IN
EXCAVATIONS AT PAWAYA DURING SAMVAT 1981.

Stone finds.

1. Piece of a big lintel of gateway. Length $6' 5\frac{1}{2}''$ $\times$ height $2' 2''$ $\times$ thickness at ends $2' 2''$ and at middle $1' 6''$. Two faces and underside carved into sculptures. The top side has rectangular socket holes which held sculptures or ornamental pieces. Three whole and parts of two socket holes exist in the present piece. This piece appears to be almost a half of the original. Beginning from the end the measurements of the holes are (1) length broken $\times$ breadth $9\frac{1}{4}''$ $\times$ depth $3\frac{1}{4}''$ (2) length $1' 5''$ $\times$ breadth $11''$ $\times$ depth $1\frac{1}{2}''$ (3) length $6''$ $\times$ breadth $4\frac{3}{4}''$ $\times$ depth $3''$ (4) length $6\frac{3}{4}''$ $\times$ breadth $5''$ $\times$ depth $3\frac{1}{4}''$ (5) length $4\frac{1}{2}''$ $\times$ breadth $4\frac{1}{2}''$ $\times$ depth $3\frac{1}{2}''$.

One of the faces has the following sculptures (1): A dance scene (2) Bali's sacrifice (3) Trivikrama Vishnu.

The other face has (1) Scene of the churning of the Ocean (2) Karttikeya (?)

2. Torso of a female.

Ht. $1' 8''$ $\times$ br. $13\frac{1}{2}''$ $\times$ thickness $1'$. Existing portion shows waist and thighs. A close fitting *lahanga* and a jewelled girdle with a buckle in the form of two crocodile heads are worn. The figure is in the round.

3. Lower part of a pot bellied figure (Kubera ?) sitting cross-legged on a pedestal. One leg only preserved. A scarf is tied round belly with a knot in front. Breadth $2' 2\frac{1}{2}''$ $\times$ height $2' 1''$ $\times$ thickness $16''$.

4. A Triratna or Trisula (?)

Ht. $2' 3''$ $\times$ br. $2' 1\frac{1}{2}''$ $\times$ thickness $7\frac{1}{2}''$, tenon $4''$ $\times$ $4\frac{1}{2}''$ $\times$ $5''$. Top damaged. The two side limbs are finished in the form of foliage. A tenon at bottom to show that it was fixed on something probably on the lintel of some gateway.

5. End of a lintel (?)

A socket or tenon at end. Both faces carved. Section oval. Each face shows a female's hand holding a twig of mango tree, surely fragment of a woman under tree which was a common *motif* of a bracket of a gateway. Height $1' 8''$ $\times$ breadth $1' 6''$ $\times$ thickness $1' 4''$, tenon $7''$ $\times$ $5''$ $\times$ $4\frac{1}{4}''$.

6. Piece of a lion conventionally carved. Length $2' 3\frac{1}{2}''$ $\times$ breadth $9''$ $\times$ height $1' 2''$.

7. A water spout in the form of a crocodile's head *in situ* in the eastern face of the brick platform.

8. Several small pieces of stone sculptures.

9. Dwarf bracket lying on top of mound.

Height $1' 7''$ $\times$ breadth $1' 5''$ $\times$ thickness $1' 8''$ bottom broken. Busts of *Kichakas* or dwarfs with upraised hands on three sides. Fourth side undressed. Faces and hands of dwarfs damaged. They wear jewelled necklaces round their necks (Gupta style), knot of a scarf is seen on the front of one of the dwarfs.

10. Sculpture of a female with a waist cloth No. 2. ...
 11. Sculpture of a torso with hand No. 4.
 12. A sculpture (piece) showing lion and snake No. 14.
 13. A sculpture No. 53
 14. A sculpture (conch) No. 71
 15. A sculpture No. 89
 16. A sculpture (head) No. 171

Terra Cotta.

17. Head of male with open mouth No. 6
 18. Head of male with beard and hair No. 7
 19. Head of male with locks of hair No. 8 ...
 20. A piece of moulded corner brick No. 11 ...
 21. A torso No. 17
 22. A piece of a moulded brick No. 18
 23. A piece of round moulded brick No. 24
 24. A sculpture with broken feet No. 31... ..
 25. A sculpture of Varaha (man) No. 32 ..
 26. A sculpture of elephant No. 34
 27. A head with beard No. 37
 28. A head with an ear ornament No. 43
 29. A bird without head No. 44
 30. A round moulded brick No. 47
 31. A neck with ornaments No. 48
 32. A man pierced with an arrow No. 58... ..
 33. A piece No. 59
 34. A bird No. 67
 35. A moulded brick No. 69... ..
 36. A head No. 76
 37. " " 80
 38. " " 82
 39. " " 84
 40. " " 83
 41. A torso " 85
 42. A hand " 87
 43. Pieces No. 88
 44. A conch piece No. 90
 45. A head No. 91
 46. A piece of pottery No. 95
 47. A piece of iron flat bar No. 96
 48. An iron nail No. 99
 49. A torso on horse back No. 100
 50. A moulded brick No. 102
 51. " " " 104
 52. A torso kneeling No. 105
 53. A moulded brick No. 111
 54. A head with ear ornament No. 112
 55. A long foot No. 114

56.	A piece No 115	...	...
57.	A brick with leaf mouldings No, 116	...	...
58.	A torso with a piece of arms and spear No, 117	...	...
59.	A piece of moulded corner brick No. 118	...	...
60.	A finely moulded piece No. 120	...	...
61.	A laughing face No. 121	...	...
62.	A moulded brick No. 122	...	...
63.	" " with lead mould No. 123	...	...
64.	A piece of carving No. 124	...	...
65.	A moulded brick No. 125	...	...
66.	A finely moulded brick No. 127	...	...
67.	" " " " 130	...	...
68.	A torso No, 131	...	...
69.	" " 132	...	...
70.	A head of parrot No. 135	...	...
71.	A head with open mouth No. 136	...	...
72.	A torso with holy thread No. 137	...	...
73.	A piece of moulded brick No. 139	...	...
74.	A torso No. 141	...	...
75.	A piece with ornament No. 142	...	...
76.	A moulded brick No. 143	...	...
77.	" " " 144	...	...
78.	" " " 146	...	...
79.	A hand with ornament No. 149	...	...
80.	Head of a female No. 153	...	...
81.	Head of a fish No. 157	...	...
82.	A moulded brick No. 164	...	...
83.	A head with hair plated No. 172	...	...
84.	A moulded brick No. 173	...	...

APPENDIX No. D.

Monuments listed in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

No.	Locality.	Name of Monument.	Class.	Ownership.
District Esagarh.				
1	Chanderi.	Mehman sarai or guest house and its gateways.	II	Government.
2	"	Bandar Baodi or monkey well ...	III	"
3	"	Qazi-ka-Bag-ki-masjid (mosque) with inscription and baodi (square)	III	Government.
4	"	Maqbara close to above	II	Government.
5	"	Chandai Baodi	II	"
6	"	Visurkund (Vishnukund ?) ...	III	"
7	"	Hatpure-ki-masjid with inscription	III	"
8	"	Jaina temple called chaubisi ...	II	Local Chaudhari & Jaina community.
9	"	Domed shrine of Siva with inscription	III	"
10	"	Mirza-ki-masjid with inscription.	III	"
11	"	Smaller Jaina temple with two old images	II	Jaina community.
12	"	Chetan Baodi	III	"
12a	"	Tomb of a Christian soldier near Harakund	III	"
12b	"	Tomb of a Christian soldier near Chaudhari's house	III	"
13	Singhpur.	Raja's mahals	III	Government.
14	Khanpura.	Sati stones with inscriptions ...	III	"
15	Gurilakapahad.	Two Jaina temples... ..	III	"
16	Naderi.	Sati stones with inscriptions ...	III	"
17	"	Ajwan Baodi with inscription ..	III	"
18	"	A ruined Jaina temple	III	"
19	Mohanpur.	Fragments of Jaina sculptures in an enclosure	III	"
20	"	Nrisinha temple in village in which some old pillars and door frames are built ..	III	"
21	"	Jaina Chaityalaya outside village.	III	"
22	Budhi-Chanderi.	Sati stone with inscription ...	III	"
23	Lakhari.	Two Saiva shrines one with an inscription	III	Government.
24	"	An old well close by	III	"
25	"	Another square baodi (old) ...	III	"
26	"	An old temple known as Madha.	III	"
27	"	Ruins of a Jaina temple	III	"
28	Bithla.	Jaina temple	II	"
29	"	Ruins of three other Jaina temples.	III	"
30	Rakhetra or Gadhelna.	A large rock-cut Jaina image known as Bhiyant or Bhimasena with inscriptions	I	Government.
31	"	A number of rock-cut Hindu sculptures and an inscription...	I	"
32	"	A natural cavern and fragments of Hindu sculptures	III	"

APPENDIX No. E.

Inscriptions copied or noticed in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object inscribed.	No. of lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	Name of ruling king.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	B u d h i - Chanderi.	Pedestal of an image of Hanuman.	4	Nagari.	District Esagarh. Hindi.	V. S. 1795 = A. C. 1738.	Durjan Singh Devs, Bondela of Chanderi.	Records the installation of the idol (?).	
2	"	A wall of a Jaina temple ...	7	"	"	"	"	"	Illegible.
3	"	A Sati stone flanking the passage to river on west.	15	"	Hindi.	V. S. 1545 Jyeshtha Vadi 5 Saturday.	Rajadhiraja Gayasuddin of Mandu.	Records Sati of (name illegible) at Nasirabad (as Budhi Chanderi was renamed by the Muhammadans). The post was erected by Ratana son of the deceased.	
4	Chanderi.	The central niche of Mirzon-ki-masjid.	5	Corrupt Nastaliq.	Persian,	"	"	"	Badly damaged.
5	"	A slab in the wall of a house on the Fort Road.	5	"	"	15th Rabi- ul-sani A.H.1051 = A. C. 1641.	Shahjahan I Mughal Em- peror of Delhi.	"	"
6	"	The lintel of door frame of a tomb in the N. E. corner of the grave yard of Nizam ud-din's family.	3	Naskh.	"	A. H. 828 = A.C.1424	Hoshang Shah of Malwa.	Records that the tomb was built during the reign of Hoshang Shah and gives the name of a saint of the time who is obviously the inmate of the tomb.	

Chanderi.	A Christian tomb	...	4	Nastaliq.	Persian.	A. H. 1 232 = A. C. 1816	Nil.	Records the death of one Yunis on 16 Jamadi-ul-sani A. H. 1232 and that the tomb was erected by the Colonel's order.
8	"	A lintel of the mosque near Mardan smith's house in bazar.	4	Naskh.	"	A. H. 795 = A. C. 1392.	Muhammad Shah s/o. Firozshah of Delhi.	Consists of 8 verses arranged in 4 lines and records that the mosque was erected during the reign of Muhammad Shah s/o. Firozshah in A. H. 795. It describes Dilawar Khan as a favourite courtier. The name of the builder though given is not clear.
9	"	A pillar of the left hand porch of the same mosque.	6	Nastaliq.	"	...	...	Illegible.
10	"	A room in the house of a Brahman named Ram Bharose.	4	Suls.	"	A. H. 711 = A. C. 1311	Ala-ud-din Muhammad Khilji of Delhi.	Records the construction of a mosque by Ismail s/o. Abdulla during the reign of Muhammad Shah in A. H. 711.
11	"	A well known as Chandai Baodi.	12	Naskh.	Persian.	...	Muhammad Sultan of Mandu.	Worn out and illegible.
12	"	"	20	Nagari.	Sanskrit.	...	"	The lower portion worn out and illegible.

Inscriptions copied or noticed in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.—(contd).

Serial No.	Locality.	Object inscribed.	No. of lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	Name of ruling king.	P u r p o r t .	R E M A R K S .
13	Chanderi.	The central niche of Shekhon-ki-masjid. Piece No. 1	3	Nastaliq.	Arabic.	...	...	Holy text.	
		" 2	3	"	"	...	...	Records that Hamid-ud-din s/o Shekh Firoz-ud-din descendant of Shekh Soleman built the mosque and the tomb in his life time during the reign of Aurangzeb the conqueror in A. H. 1094.	
		" 3	4	"	Persian	A. H. 1094 A.C. = 1682	Aurangzeb		
14	"	The arch of door frame of a tomb in the graveyard of Shekhas.	1	"	"	A. H. 1064 A.C. = 1653	...	...	No t legible.
15	"	The central niche of Kazi-ki-masjid in Kazi-ka-bagh. Piece No. 1	4	"	"	...	A. H. 1113 A.C. = 1701	Records that Raja Durjan Singh owner of the estate bestowed this garden. And that through God's grace the mosque and well reached completion during the reign of Alamgir. Further records that Abda s/o Suleman built a tomb near the tomb of Suleman.	

17	Chanderi.	Piece No. 2	...	5	"	"	...	Regnal year 45 of Alamgir.	...	Aurangzeb of Dehli.	...	Not yet deciphered.
16	"	" 3	...	4	"	"	Persian.		...		...	Not yet deciphered.
17	"	A niche in Kazi Baodi...		8	Naskh.	"				Aurangzeb.		Records that a well, mosque and a garden were completed by Azam Khan during the reign of Aurangzeb A. H. 1102. Regnal year 35.
18	"	Hukki mosque in Hat-kapura.		6	Nastaliq.	"		A. H. 1102 = A. C. 1690				
19	"	A Cross set up at the head of a Christian tomb near Harkund.		6	Roman.	French ?		1819 A. C				Not yet deciphered.
20	"	Carved on rock near Jagesvari Devi.		7	Nagari.	...		V. S. 1743 = A. C. 1686				Not legible
21	"	A madhi (Shrine of Siva) in the field known as Dariba Baodi.		23	"	Sanskrit.		Monday Magha Sudi 8 V. S. 1724 = A. C. 1667.				A Prasasti recording the installation of a Siva Linga known as Manasimhesvara by Sri Manasimha s/o Sri Kasivara Chakravarti Vikramaditya, while he was Yivaraja, Composed by Giridhara Jyotirvid devotee of Jagesvari and engraved by Devidasa.
22	Khanpur.	A Sati pillar near the eastern boundary of the village.		9	"	...		V. S. 1545 (?)				Illegible.
23	Lakhari.	A loose slab found in a baodi and now preserved in the Archeological Museum at Gwalior.		6	"	Incorrect Sanskrit.		V. S. 1124 = A. C. 1067		Sri Abhayadeva (?)		The purport is not clear. Mentions king Abhayadeva (?) Prince Chandraditya and Jalhanade [vi] (?).

APPENDIX No. E.

Inscriptions copied or noticed in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.—(contd).

Serial No.	Locality.	Object inscribed.	No. of lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	Name of ruling king.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
23	Lakhari.	The lintel of a door frame of a ruined temple.	2	Nagari.	Incorrect Sanskrit.	V. S. 1000[?]	Not clear.	Apparently a pilgrim's record. Records 3 names Sri Gabhu Thakur, Sri Yavakasya Deva and his mother Chhita (Sita ?)	The date is recorded but in a very confused manner. The word <i>is</i> <i>Samvat</i> <i>sarya</i> <i>sak</i> <i>esha</i> <i>100,10</i> <i>sahasre</i> <i>shu</i> Literally it means ten thousand years. What the writer probably meant to express was Samvat 1000. Sayyad Alim Shah reigned at Delhi from 1443 to 1451 A. C. He was perhaps the Governor at Chanderi at the time of our inscription. In the date the figures showing the century are not expressed; from the style of letters the record is not less than 5 or 6 centuries old.
24	Naderi.	Sati stone near a well known as Dhimra.	6	"	Sanskrit.	Thursday Jyeshtha vadi 14 V. S. 1485 Saka 1350 = A. C. 1428.	Sahi Alim (Sayyed of Delhi.)	Records the Sati of a Luhar (black-smith) at village Gular from which the neighbouring hill probably takes its name Gurila-ka-Pahad.	
25	"	Another Sati on a platform in village.	4	"	"	V. S. 0066	...	A Sati record.	

26	Naderi.	In a niche in Ajwan baodi.	26	Nagari.	Sanskrit.	Not clear.	Mahamud Khilji of Malwa or per- haps his son.	Records construction of the baodi by (names illegible; genealogy of donor given).	Mostly illegible.
27	Rakhetra (Bhiyadant)	Pedestal of a big rock cut Jaina sculpture of Adinatha	1	"	...	...	...	Pilgrim's record.	Illegible.
28	"	A tablet above foot- prints in rock near the big Jaina sculpture.	5	"	"	Friday Phalguna Sudi 2 V.S. 1555 = A.C. 1498	Sultan Gayaa- ud-din.	Records the making of the foot-prints of Sri Visala Raj pupil of Upadhyaya Manika Sandara papil of Upadhyaya Malaya Chanda Suri by Muniraja.	
29	"	The seat of a big Jaina image of Adinatha. See No. 27 above.	2	"	...	Saturday Ashadha vadi 8 V.S. 1675 = A.C. 1618	...	Pilgrim's record. Mentions Chanderi and Bithla which is the same as the present Vithala Village.	Illegible.
30	"	Rock	1	"	...	...	...	Pilgrim's record.	"
31	"	"	1	"	...	...	...	"	
32	"	A tablet in rock	5	"	Sanskrit.	Asvina vadi 30 V. S. 999 = A.C. 942 Bhadrapada sudi 3 V.S. 1000 and Kartika V. S. 1000 = A. C. 943	Not clear.	The purport is not quite clear. Apparently records the con- struction of some water or irrigation work in connection with the Orr river by Sri Vinayaka Pala Deva whose identity is uncertain. He may perhaps be the prince of the same name as men- tioned at the end of the Khajuraha stone inscription of Samvat 1011 (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> Vol. I. P. 124.	

Inscriptions copied or noticed in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.—(contd).

Serial No.	Locality.	Object inscribed.	No. of lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	Name of ruling king.	Purpose.	REMARKS.
33	Singhpur a hamlet near Ram- nagar Mahal.	A baodi known as Raja- mati.	36	Nagari.	Sanskrit and Prakrit.	Thursday Magha sudi 5 V. S. 1525 = A.C. 1468	Gayas-ud-din Sultan of Mandu.	Mentions a Sri Gopagirindra i. e., king of Gwalior whose name however is not recorded. Records an amount namely 95 crores in figures and 96 crores in words, but of what coin is not clear. Perhaps it refers to the amount spent on the works. The Prasasti was written by Bhailadaman son of Sri Krisnaraja.	
34	"	A Sati near Chanderi, on Mungaoli-Chanderi Road.	18	"	Sanskrit.	V. S. 1682 = A.C. 1625	...	Records the construction of a well.	A Sati record of a Srivastava Kayastha lady whose name is illegible.
35	Singhpur (this is an- other village 2 m. north- east of Chanderi.)	A loose slab dug out of the tank in front of Singhpur Mahal.	11	Naskh.	Persian.	A. H. 836 = A.C. 1432	Hoshang Shah of Mandu.	Records that the tank was completed on 10th Shavval A. H. 836 during the reign of Hoshang Shah.	

Inscriptions copied or noticed in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25---(contd).

Serial No.	Locality.	Object inscribed.	No of lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	Name of ruling king.	P u r p o r t .	R E M A R K S .
44	Narwar Fort.	A loose slab found in the yard of Dargah of Madar Shah.	10	Naskh and Nastaliq.	Arabic and Persian.	A. H. 960 = A.C.1552	Muhammad Adil [of Suri Dynasty of Dehli] and Dilawar Khan as his assistant (i. e., Govern or).	The inscription consists of 10 lines, 6 of which are in Naskh characters and Arabic language and are quotations from holy texts. The remaining 4 are in Nastaliq and Persian and record the construction of mosque by order of Dilawar Khan during the reign of Muhammad Adil. (I. A. Vol. L V I P, 101).	
45	"	Over the mihrabs of prayer hall in a mosque near Hawa Pour.	...	...	...	...	...	..	Not copied yet.
		Central mihrab	4	Naskh.	Arabic.	...	...	Quotation from holy texts.	
		" (below the above)...	4	"	Persian.	900 A. H. = A.C.1494	...	Bears date and some name not deciphered yet.	
		North mihrab	4	"	Arabic.	...	...	Quotation from holy texts.	
		South mihrab	4	"	"	...	...	"	

				District	Ujjain.			
46	Ujjain.	A loose slab in Madhav College at Ujjain.	10 and margin.	Naskh and Nastaliq.	Arabic and Persian.	A.H. 986 = A.C.1578	Akbar the Great of Delhi.	The margin has a line of holy text on all sides except the bottom in Naskh. 10 lines in body are in prose in Nastaliq. Records the construction of a strong <i>Sarai</i> during the reign of Akbar whose eulogy is also recorded. The date is given in two chronograms on Abjad System and below them in numerals also. (<i>I.A. Vol. LVI.</i>)
47	"	Fragment of a black slab (slate) unearthed in dismantling a house in the Town Improvement operations and now in the possession of Sriyut Surya Narayanaji Vyasa.	4	Nagari.	Sanskrit.	...	...	Tentative reading. १. संचय-शुभं-युरजायतो र्थी । रत्न-प्रकरजल वयस्य [सं] पत्रकप-घा..... २. ता. ॥ [२६९] ॥ तस्मिन्नावर्जित-सुरजनप्रौढवर्गं सुधर्मा मध्या-सीने हरति मघवत्स्वर्गं सामाज्य. ३. संपदो न व्यापारगतिः कियत्य-पिच यस्यालिंगितुं शम्य (तो) मर्यादा परि. ४. मकं चिवेकादूरसिधिरसि कंडे नेत्रयोरदघाति ॥२७३॥ यत्पादा-भुजनिर्मितप्रणतयो.
48	"	Another fragment of the same as above.	13	"	"	...	...	१.....२ वगाह्य सरयूं जित्वाश्रमं सैनिकैः साके तो पयना वनीषु कलि क्रमं नीते कांतैः सह मलयशैले युवतिभिः । यदातंकाह्लंका [वि]

APPENDIX No. F.

List of coins examined during Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

No.	Name of king and dynasty.	Metal.	No. of coins examined.	Remarks.
Gupta Dynasty.				
1	Chandragupta II	Gold	5	
Sultans of Jaunpur.				
2	Muhammad Shah	Copper	13	
Mughal Emperors of Delhi.				
3	Shahjahan I	Silver	2	
4	Shah Alam II	"	15	
5	Muhammad Akbar III	"	1	
Miscellaneous.				
6	Modern coins of Europe including Portugal, Austria, France, U. S. A., and colonies.	Silver	12	
7	"	Copper	28	
8	Scindias of Gwalior, from Mahadaji to Madhav Rao	Silver	27	
9	Jiwaji Rao Scindia	Copper	697	
10	Bhopal State	"	66	
11	Hyderabad State	"	1	
12	Dhar State	"	1	
13	Indore "	"	1	
14	Bharatpur State	"	1	
15	Tonk "	"	2	
16	Kotah "	"	2	
17	Bundi "	"	1	
18	Jaipur "	"	1	
19	Orcha "	"	4	
20	Damaged and undecipherable	Silver	44	
21	" "	Copper	483	
		Total ...	1,407	only.

APPENDIX No. G.

List of antiquities added to Archaeological Museum in
Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Remark.
Old Paintings.			
1		A Muhammadan king seated on throne under <i>chhatra</i> (supposed to be Aurangzeb).	
2		Maharaja Amarsingh standing.	
3		A princess going to meet her expected lover in her garden house, with maids etc.	
4		Lord Krishna playing on his flute.	
5		A fairy leading a tiger driven by a bull-headed demon.	
6		A river side scene with a water bird pounced upon by a hawk.	
7		A seated noble.	
8		Two nobles with attendants seated (upper panel), naked boys (?) playing (middle panel), three ladies (lower panel).	
9		River goddess Ganga mounted on crocodile.	
10		A lady worshipping a tree followed by her maid-servant.	
11		A noble man in arms on horse back with attendants.	
12		Lakshmi Narayana.	
13		A seated noble.	
14		Ganesa and Parvati.	
15		Ganesa seated on a throne with Sarasvati on a swan.	
16		A Nawab of Jhajhar driving in a four wheeled carriage followed by mounted body-guards.	
17		Fortress of Gwalior (water colour painting by General Popham, A. D. 1780.)	Printed.
18		Fortress of Gwalior in water colour, south side view published 1787.	
19		" Wood "	
20		A piece of carved bamboo, size, 10" x 4 $\frac{3}{4}$ "	
Stone sculptures.			
21		A black stone sculpture of Siva and Parvati size 8 $\frac{3}{4}$ " x 6 $\frac{1}{2}$ " x 2".	
22	Gyaras-pur.	Parvati standing.	
23	"	Siva killing demon Gaja.	
24	"	Fish incarnation of Vishnu.	
25	Bhilsa.	Jaina <i>Tirthamkara</i> .	
26	Gurilakn-pahad.	Bhairava.	
27	Jharna.	A Trisula.	
Inscriptions.			
28	Lakhari.	A Sanskrit inscription dated V. S. 1124	
29	Singhpur.	A Persian inscription dated A. H. 828, ...	
Coins.			
30-150		Gold, Silver and Copper.	

APPENDIX No. H.

List of photographs taken in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

No.	Place.		Subject.	Size.	REMARKS
District Amjhera.					
1	Bagh.	Caves,	general view from north ...	Full.	
2	"	Cave No. 2	" " " ...	"	
3	"	" "	another " " ...	"	
4	"	" "	view of verandah pillars ...	"	
5	"	" "	front view of verandah ...	"	
6	"	" "	interior view, central ...	"	
7	"	" "	" cross view showing pillars ...	"	Duplicate,
8	"	" "	right hand row of pillars in interior ...	"	
9	"	" "	Dagoba and Bodhisattvas flanking door of chapel...	"	
10	"	" "	group of sculptures of Buddha and attendants on the right side wall of antechamber ...	"	
11	"	" "	" " left side " ...	"	
12	"	" 4	view of facade from north- west ...	"	
13	"	" "	principal doorframe ...	"	Duplicate.
14	"	" "	interior view showing a frieze ...	"	
15	"	" "	interior " " pillar...	"	
16	"	" "	" " " bracket.	Half.	
17	"	" "	newly discovered fresco painting ...	"	
18	"	" "	part of newly " "	"	
19	"	" "	sculpture of a Naga king and queen ...	Full.	
20	"	" "	chapel of Nagas ...	"	
21	"	" "	sculpture of Kubera (?) ...	"	
22	"	" 4 & 5	general view from north.	"	
23	"	" 5	facade from north east...	"	
24	"	" "	interior view, general ...	"	
25	"	" "	" showing pillars ...	"	
District Bhilsa.					
26	Badoh.	Gadarmal temple	general view from north- west.	"	
27	"	" "	" " " " east.	"	
28	"	" "	near view from north ...	"	
29	"	" "	near view from north- east ...	"	
30	"	" "	porch from north-west ...	"	
31	"	" "	basement from north- east ...	Full.	
32	"	Jaina temple,	general view from north- west ...	"	

No.	Place.	Subject.	Size.	REMARKS.
33	Badoh.	Solah khambi, general view from south-west	Full.	
34	Besnagar.	Khamb.baba, general view from south-west	"	
35	Udaygiri.	Cave No. 5, sculpture of Varaha (Boar incarnation)		
36	"	Cave No. 5, Sculpture of the goddess of Earth being lifted up by Boar ...	Half.	
37	"	Cave No. 6, door frame	Full.	
38	"	" image of Vishnu	Half.	
39	"	" another image of Vishnu	"	
40	"	" image of Mahishasuramardini	"	
41	Udaypur.	Udayesvar temple after repairs, view from south east	Full.	
42	"	" " back view	"	
43	"	" " vedi after repairs	"	
District Esagarh.				
44	Rakhetra.	Rock-cut sculpture of a Jaina Tirthankara locally known as Bhimasena or Bhiyadant	Half.	
45	"	Rock-cut group of Brahma, Vishnu (Varaha) and Mahesa.	"	
46	"	" " of a Siva and Parvati in a niche... ..	"	
47	Bithla.	Jaina temple, general view from south-west	Full.	
48	Budhi Chanderi	Group of Jaina temples, general view from south west	"	
49	"	" " a door frame	Half.	
50	"	Jaina sculptures in ruins	Full.	
51	"	" " arranged in the courtyard of a temple.	"	
52	"	" " " " " " " " " " " "	"	
53	"	" " big image of Santinatha in the interior of a temple	"	
54	"	" " attendants of Santinatha	Half.	
55	Chanderi.	Town, bird's eye view from Fort	Full.	
56	"	" another view from top of a house.	Half.	
57	"	Fort, general view (near) from west.	Full.	
58	"	" " (distant) " " " "	"	
59	"	" " " " from Dhobi Talao...	"	
60	"	" Rest house from south-west	"	
61	"	" Rajaka mahal from south-west	"	
62	"	" " " " " " " " " " " "	Half.	
63	"	" Mosque, carved niches in interior... ..	Full.	
64	"	Madarsa, before repairs, general view from south east	Full.	
65	"	" after " " " " " " " " " "	"	
66	"	" after repairs, another view	"	
67	"	Shahzadika Roza, before repairs, general view south-east	"	
68	"	" " after " " " " " "	"	
69	"	" " interior view	"	

No.	Place.	Subject.	Size.	REMARKS.
70	Chanderi	Delhi gate, view of north ...	Full.	
71	"	" " inscription ...	Half.	
72	"	Tombs of Nizamuddin's family, a door frame.	Full.	
73	"	" " " part of a door frame.	"	
74	"	" " " a carved niche.	"	
75	"	" " " carving work on a wall.	Half.	
76	"	Jhinjharia Pir, interior view ...	Full.	
77	"	Parmesvari tal, view from East ...	"	
78	"	A carved tomb stone ...	"	
79	"	" " " another view ...	"	
80	"	A lamp post in a tomb ...	Half.	
81	"	Panchmadhi, general view from north-east ...	Full.	
82	"	Mehmansarai, east gate ...	"	
83	"	" north gate ...	"	
84	"	Textile Institute, view of machinery ...	"	
85	"	Gate way near Chaudhari's house, from north-east ...	"	
86	"	Chandai baodi, a corner view ...	"	
87	"	Kati ghati, before repairs, from south ...	"	
88	"	" " after " " " " ...	"	
89	"	" " " " north ...	"	
90	"	Battisi baodi, corner view from n.-east.	"	
91	"	" " " " n.-west.	"	
92	"	" " inscription over lintel ...	Half.	
93	"	" " in niche ...	Full.	
94	"	" " in another niche ...	"	
95	"	Shekhon-ka-maqbara, carving work ...	Half.	
96	"	Christian tomb, near Chaudhari's house.	"	
97	"	" " near Hara kund ...	"	
98	"	Idgah, inscription ...	"	
99	"	Gol baodi, Inscription in niche ...	"	
100	"	" " in another niche, ...	"	
101	"	Hanuman temple on fort hill, inscription.	"	
102	"	Ram Bharose's house, inscription	"	
103	"	Jamah masjid, inscription ...	"	
104	"	Horse's tomb ...	"	
105	Fatehabad	Koshak mahal, general view from north east.	Full.	Duplicate.
106	"	" " front view ...	"	
107	"	" " interior corner view.	"	
108	"	" " interior big arches from west.	"	
109	Pancham-nagar.	Old palace after repairs, general view from north-east.	"	
110	Singhpur.	" " repairs, general view from south.	"	
111	Gurila Hill	A group of sculptures in a ruined Jaina temple.	Half.	

No.	Place.	Subject.	Size.	REMARKS.
156	Archaeological Museum, Gwl.	Bagh Drawings Cave No. 4, dagoba ...	Full.	
157	"	" " 5 and 6, plan. ...	"	
158	"	" " " section ...	"	
159	"	" " " pillar ...	"	
160	"	" " " No. 7, pillars ...	"	
161	"	Gwalior Fort, map with titles in Hindi.	"	
162	"	" " sketch from south ...	Half.	
163	"	" " " north-west.	"	
164	"	" " sketch by General Popham.	"	
165	"	Udaypur—Stone inscription (impression) of Naravarman Paramara.	Full.	
166	"	Buddha avatars of Vishnu, from Sunari	"	
167	"	Mother and baby (Krishna Yasoda), front view, from Badoh.	"	
168	"	Mother and baby (Krishna Yasoda), side view, from Badoh.	Full.	
169	"	Rudra standing, from Kota (Udhamdeka)	"	
170	"	Mother goddess, from Besnagar ...	"	
171	"	" " (another)	"	
172	"	" " " " ...	"	
173	"	Five small pieces, from Badoh ...	Half.	
174	"	A goddess standing, from Badoh ...	"	
175	"	A woman with a baby, from Badoh ...	"	
176	"	Sankha or conch, from Badoh ...	"	
177	"	Surya seated, from Padhavli ...	"	
178	"	" " in a charriot, from Padhavli	"	
179	"	Ganga, from Tumain ...	"	
180	"	Bust of Parvati, from Bhilsa ...	"	
181	"	Ashtadikpalas, from Badoh ...	"	
182	"	Two seated images, from Gwalior ...	"	
183	"	Lower part of a seated Ascetic, from Naresar.	"	
184	"	A Standing torso and a bust of a goddess, from Badoh.	"	
185	"	A hunting scene, from Badoh. ...	"	
186	"	A bust of a female, " ...	"	
187	"	A dancing Ganesa, from Gadhi Barod.	"	
188	"	Ganesa standing, from Gwalior Fort.	"	
189	"	Torso of a male figure standing, from Udaygiri.	"	
190	"	Torso of a male figure standing, from Bhilsa.	"	
191	"	Kubera standing, from Besnagar ...	"	
192	"	Vishnu standing, " excavations.	"	
193	"	Bust of Siva standing, from Badoh ...	"	
194	"	Parvati with baby, from Tumain ...	"	
195	"	Yama standing, from Kota (Udhamdeka)	"	
196	"	Kubera seated, from Tumain ...	"	
197	"	Kubera and Riddhi seated, from Badoh	"	
198	"	Kubera standing and a woman, from Gwalior Fort.	"	
199	"	Hanuman standing, from Gwalior Fort	"	
200	"	Two flying figures, from Sondni ...	"	

No.	Place.	Subject.	Size,	REMARKS.
201	Archæological Museum.	Two elephants, from Gwalior ...	Half.	
202	"	Fragment of an image, from Badoh...	"	
203	"	A man playing on a tabor, from Badoh	"	
204	"	Varahi and a female bust	"	
205	"	Torso of a female and another piece, from Badoh.	"	
206	"	Marriage of Siva and Parvati, from Padhavli.	"	
207	"	Siva standing, from Kotah ...	"	
208	"	Bust of Trimurti, from Padhavli ...	"	
209	"	Bust of Indra, from Badoh ...	"	
210	"	Hari-Hara standing, from Ghusai ..	"	
211	"	Nrisimha standing, from Besnagar ...	"	
212	"	Kumara standing, from Kota (Ud.)...	"	
213	"	Kaumari standing " " ...	"	
214	"	Brahmani standing " " ...	"	
215	"	Siva and Parvati ...	"	
District Mandasor.				
216	Khilchipura.	Yamuna on Torana pillar Sravan Kawad	"	Dupli.
District Ujjain.				
217	Kaliadeh.	Water palace, distant view from north-east.	Full.	
218	"	" near view from south- west.	"	
219	"	" near view from south- east.	"	
220	"	" near view from north- east.	"	
221	"	" near view from north- west.	"	
222	"	" interior arcade of water chambers.	"	
223	Ujjain	Chaubis Khamba, from north ...	"	
224	"	Vridha Kalesvara, from south-east.	"	
225	"	Mahakalesvara, from south-east ...	"	
226	"	Persian inscription (loose) preserved in Madhava College.	"	
227	"	Sanskrit inscription (loose) preserved in Madhava College.	"	
228	"	Jaisingh's Astronomical Observatory, general view from north.	"	
229	"	Jaisingh's Astronomical Observatory general view from south-west.	"	
230	"	Jaisingh's Astronomical Observatory, showing Digimsha Yantra from north.	"	
231	"	Jaisingh's Astronomical Observatory showing Nadivalaya Yantra and Dakshino Vritti Yantra from north-east.	"	

No.	Place.	Subject.	Size.	REMARKS.
Miscellaneous.				
232	Sanchi (Bhopal State)	Buddhist stupa No. 1, general view from south-east.	Full.	
233	"	" " general view from north-east.	"	
234	"	" " eastern gateway	"	
235	"	" " eastern gateway another view.	"	
236	"	" " detail of a pillar	"	
237	"	" No. 3 general view from south.	Half.	
238	"	Gupta temple, general view from north-east.	Full.	
239	Muradpur (Kurwai State)	Varaha (animal shaped)	...	"
240	"	A seated monkey goddess	...	Quarter.
241	Chanderi.	Topo sheet copied ...	...	Full.
242	"	Topo sheet copied ...	...	Half.
243		Astronomical instruments	...	Full.
244		Painting showing a bird flying over a river.	"	Dupli.
245		" " lion led by a fairy and a demon.	"	
246		" " a Muhammadan saint and a she-buffalo.	Half.	
247		" of Radha Krishna	...	"
248		" showing (1) Krishna and cows and (2) scene of bathing.	"	
249		" showing Siva with two females on throne and three female attendants.	"	

APPENDIX No. I.

List of lantern slides made during
Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

No.	Description.	Copying negative if any.	REMARKS.
Gateways.			
1	North gateway of Buddhist stupa No. 1 at Sanchi.		
2	Elephant gate, Gwalior Fort.		
Rock-cut caves.			
3	Interior of cave No. 2, at Bagh.		
4	Varaha cave at Udaygiri.		
Temples.			
5	Temple No. 1 at Surwaya	1	
6	" " " Doorframe.		
Buddhist Sculptures.			
7	Bodhisatva Maitrya seated	1	
8	" " standing	1	
9	" " Simhanada	1	
10	" " seated (Gandhara)	1	
11	Buddha (seated) Lucknow Museum	1	
12	" in abhaya mudra	1	
13	" in dharma-chakra mudra	1	
14	" standing	1	
15	" practising penance	1	
16	" leaving his capital in renunciation	1	
17	" Mara's army marching to disturb penance of.	1	
18	Kubera and Hariti	1	
19	Naga Raja	1	
20	Manjusri or goddess of wisdom... ..	1	
21	Dvarapala from a gateway of stupa No. 1 at Sanchi.	1	
Jaina sculptures.			
22	Tirthankara Parsvanatha standing from Budhi Chanderi.		
23	" " seated " "	1	
24	" " " Gwalior Museum	1	
25	A seat of a Tirthankara, Gwalior Museum	1	
26	A Chaumukha, Gwalior Museum	1	
27	A goddess	1	
Hindu sculptures.			
28	Brahma	1	
29	Vishnu Seshasayi (sleeping on serpent)	1	
30	Vishnu riding on Garuda	1	

No.	Description.	Copying negative if any	REMARKS.
31	Siva standing, from Gwalior Museum ...	1	
32	" " another " ...	1	
33	" Tandava (in bronze) ...	1	
34	" " (another) ...	1	
35	" Linga ...	1	
36	" and Parvati standing ...	1	
37	Marriage of Siva and Parvati ...	1	
38	Siva and Parvati seated ...	1	
39	Hari-Hara ...	1	
40	Trimurti (bust) ...	1	
41	" standing ...	1	
42	Ganesa dancing ...	1	
43	Kurma avatara ...	1	
44	" " from Gwalior Museum ...	1	
45	" " " " ...	1	
46	Varaha " (animal) ...	1	
47	Nrisimha " ...	1	
48	Vamana " ...	1	
49	Trivikrama avatara ...	1	
50	Balarama " ...	1	
51	Buddha avatara of Vishnu ...	1	
52	River goddess Ganga ...	1	
53	River goddess Yamuna ...	1	
54	Surya seated ...	1	
55	Surya seated in chariot ...	1	
56	Goddess Mahishasuramardini ...	1	
57	Yama standing ...	1	
58	Agni " ...	1	
59	Kubera standing ...	1	
60	Indrani " ...	1	
61	Kumara " ...	1	
62	Ashta Dikpalas ...	1	
63	Nava Grabhas (nine planets) ...	1	
64	Rahu and Ketu ...	1	
65	Nandi standing ...	1	
66	Varahi and a female bust ...	1	
67	Flying angels ...	1	
68	Mother and child on a couch ...	1	
69	Kumara standing ...	1	
Miscellaneous.			
70	Bagh painting discourse in outline ...	1	
71	H. H. M. Jayaji Rao with a Hindi motto ...	1	Co
72	" " " Balaravi ...	1	Dupl.
73	Welcome ...	1	
74	Goodnight ...	1	

APPENDIX No. J.

**List of books added to the Office library, during
Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.**

No.	Title.	Remarks.
Archaeological Survey Reports, Memoirs etc.		
1	Archaeological Survey of India, Annual Report for 1921-22.	Presented.
2	Report of the Supdt. of Arch. Surv. of Burma for the year ending 31st March 1925.	"
3	Arch. Surv. of Ceylon, Annual Report for 1922-23.	"
4	" " " " " " " " 1923-24	"
5	Annul Report of the Mysore Arch. Department for 1924.	"
6	Arch. Surv. of India, Index to Annual Reports for 1902-16.	"
7	Memoirs No. 13 (Kannad Poets mentioned in inscriptions.	"
8	" No. 16 (The temple of Siva at Bhumara by R. D. Banerji).	"
9	" No. 17 (Pallava Architecture Part I by A. H. Longhurst).	"
10	" No. 19 (Hindu astronomy).	"
11	" of the Arch. Surv. of Ceylon, Vol. I, by A. M. Hocart.	"
12	" of the Arch. Surv. of Kashmir No. 1. (Antiquities of Marve-Wadwan) by R.C. Kak	"
13	" (Stone age in Kashmir), by R. C. Kak. ...	"
14	Annual Report of the Watson Museum of Antiquities for 1923-24.	"
15	Archæology in Gwalior, published by Arch. Deptt. Gwalior.	"
16-17	Ruins of Desert Cathey Vol. I and II by M. A. Stein.	Purchased.
Art, Sculpture and Painting.		
18	Conference of Indian Art held at the British Empire Exhibition on 2nd June 1924.	Presented.
19	Some reflections on an Indian Art Renaissance by the Earl of Ronaldshay.	"
20	The Influence of Indian Art... ..	"
21	Indian Art and letters Vol. I, May 1925... ..	"
22	Indian Art at the British Empire Exhibition 1924 ...	"
23	Indian Paintings under the Mughals by Percy Brown.	Purchased.
24-25	Catalogue of the Indian Collections in the Museum of Fine Arts Boston, Part I and II, By. Dr. Coomarswamy.	"
26	Do Part IV. by Dr. Coomarswamy ...	"

No.	Title.	Remarks.
27	The Himalayas in Indian Art by E. B. Havell ...	Purchased.
28	Indian Images vol. I by B.C. Bhattacharya ...	"
29	Grundzuge Der Indischenkunst by St. Kramrisch ...	"
30	The Buddha story in stone by A. H. Hargreaves ...	"
Bibliography.		
31	Supplement to the Catalogue of Books in the Secretariat General Library at Moti-mahal Part I.	"
32	Catalogue of Books in the Secretariat General Library at Shivpuri.	"
Epigraphy.		
33	Epigraphia Indo Moslemica year 1915-16... ..	Purchased.
34	" " " " 1917-18... ..	"
35	" " " " 1919-20... ..	"
36	" Indica Vol. X Part VII. July 1924 ...	Presented.
37	" " Vol. XV. No. VIII. Oct. 1924 ...	"
38	Annual Report on South Indian Epigraphy for the year ending 31st March 1924.	"
History.		
39	The travels of Fa-Hien retranslated by H. A. Giles ...	Purchased.
40	Sind the Unhappy Valley by E. A. W. Budge.	
Journals and Periodicals.		
41-54	Indian Antiquary from May 1924 to June 1925 ...	"
55	Index to Vol. LIII. 1924 Indian Antiquary ...	"
56-58	Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland for January, July and October 1924.	"
59-62	Journal of the Mythic Society, Vol. XIV No. 4 and Vol. XV. No. 1, 2, 3.	"
63-74	Modern Review from July 1924 to June 1925 ...	"
75-77	Rupam Nos. 18, 19 and 20 ...	"
78	The Indian Historical Quarterly Vol. I No. 1, March 1925.	"
79	Shama' a Magazine of Art, Literature etc. Vol. IV. No. 4. July 1924.	"
80	The Times of India, Annual 1925 ...	"
81	The Illustrated London News Sept. 27, 1924 ...	"
82	" " " " " 20, 1924 ...	"
83	The Madras Mail Annual 1924 ...	"
Literature.		
84	Samaranganasutradhara Vol. I By King Bhojadeva ...	"
85-86	The Kadambari of Banabhatta two volumes by P. V. Kane.	Purchased
87	Classical Sanskrit literature by A. B. Keith ...	"
88	Sanskrit Drama its Origin, Development, Theory and Practice by A.B. Keith	"

No.	Title.	Remarks.
Numismatics.		
89	Numismatic Notes and Monographs edited by Sydney P. Nots,	Purchased.
90	Catalogue of the coins of the Guptas, Maukharis etc. in the Provincial Museum, Lucknow.	"
91	Lectures on Ancient Indian Numismatics 1924, by D. R. Bhandarkar,	"
Iconography.		
92	Buddhist Iconography by B. Bhattacharya ...	"
State Publications.		
93	Administration Report of the Gwalior State during the year 1921-22	Presented.
94	" " " 1922-23...	"
95	General Statistics of Gwalior State for Samvat 1974 ...	"
96	List of villages by J. N. Datta.	"
97	Memorandum No. 32 बाबत न ठंडे होने ताजिये बरोज अशरह व मुकाम उज्जैन.	"
98	" No. 33 बाबत खास फरायज ऑफिसरान	"
99	" 34 ऑफिसरान की अदम तवज्जह और लापरवाई की चन्द नजीरे.	"
100	" No. 35 हिदायत व ख्यालात दरबार बाबत हार्स ब्रीडिंग फार्म व दीगर कारखाने जात	"
101	मेधिया कानफ्रेन्स.	"
102	Selections of Darbar orders for Samvat 1980 ...	"
Miscellaneous.		
103	Bibliotheca Asiatica No. 452, year 1924 ...	"

APPENDIX No. K.

Statement of income realised in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

No.	Heads.	Amount.			REMARKS.
		Rs.	a.	p.	
1	By sale of Gwalior Fort Albums ...	70	5	0	
2	„ photo prints ...	83	13	0	
3	„ tender forms ...	16	0	0	
4	Auction of mango grove at Khokhai monastery, Ranod.	6	14	0	
	Total	177	0	0	

APPENDIX. No. L.

List of expenditure incurred in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

No.	Heads.	Amount spent current year.			Amount spent last year			Total.		
		Rs.	a.	p.	Rs.	a.	p.	Rs.	a.	p.
1	Salaries	8,491	9	5	...	...	...	8,491	9	5
2	Travelling allowances ...	2,542	4	9	...	...	...	2,542	4	9
3	Contingencies ...	1,060	8	2	13	6	6	1,073	14	8
4	Books and Periodicals ...	392	13	3	85	7	9	478	5	0
5	Museum ...	1,001	10	0	98	0	0	1,099	10	0
6	Works ...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
	(1) Conservation proper ...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
	(a) Katighati at Chanderi	739	15	0	...	...	...	739	15	0
	(b) Delhi gate " ...	16	8	0	...	...	...	16	8	0
	(c) Madarsa " ...	136	5	0	...	...	...	136	5	0
	(d) Yasodarman's pillars at Sondni.	24	0	0	...	...	...	24	0	0
	(e) Jaina temple at Budhi Chanderi.	15	8	0	...	...	...	15	8	0
	(f) Clearance of caves at Bagh.	2,099	5	6	3	14	9	2,103	4	3
	(g) Minor monuments at Chanderi.	428	7	6	...	...	...	428	7	6
	(h) Fixing sign-boards ...	5	0	0	...	...	...	5	0	0
	(i) Gupta sculpture in Mandasor fort.	28	0	0	...	...	...	28	0	0
	(j) Gumbaz-ka-maqbara	...	...	...	6	0	0	6	0	0
	(k) Bijamandal mosque	...	...	...	5	7	6	5	7	6
	(l) Copying frescoes at Bagh.	...	...	...	337	4	6	337	4	6
	(m) Udayesvar temple ...	...	...	...	2,074	5	0	2,074	5	0
	(n) Khokhai temple ...	50	6	0	40	0	0	90	6	0
	(o) Gadarmal temple at Badoh.	...	...	...	62	8	0	62	8	0
	(p) Sola khambi at Badoh	...	...	...	8	0	0	8	0	0
	(q) Ujjain Observatory...	...	...	...	6,568	10	0	6,568	10	0
	(r) Jaina temple at Badoh	...	...	...	25	0	0	25	0	0
	(s) Minor monuments at Narwar.	39	10	3	...	...	...	39	10	3
	(2) Salaries of work charged staff.	307	0	6	...	...	...	307	0	6
	(3) Dr. J. H. Cousin's visit to Bagh caves.	298	11	0	...	...	...	298	11	0
	(4) D. G. A.'s visit to Bagh caves,	199	14	0	...	...	...	199	14	0
	(5) Excavations ...	1,096	9	0	154	6	9	1,250	15	9
	(6) Sending frescoes to England.	187	9	0	...	...	...	187	9	0
7	Publication of Gwalior Fort Albums ...	...	...	...	146	10	6	146	10	6
8	Special grant for Narwar Fort works.	16,824	13	6	...	...	...	16,824	13	6
9	Miscellaneous ...	414	13	9	2	14	0	417	11	9
10	Expenditure over and above Budget grant ...	159	0	0	...	...	...	159	0	0
	Grand Total.	36,570	6	1	9,621	15	3	46,192	5	4

(a) Cave No. 2 at Bagh, interior corner view.

(b) Cave No. 2 at Bagh, Dagoba shrine.

(a) Cave No. 4 at Bagh, facade.

(b) Cave No. 4 at Bagh, a porch.

(a) Karighati (rockcut gateway) at Chanderi.

(b) Badal Mahal gateway at Chanderi.

(a) Jain Images at Budhi (old) Chanderi.

(b) Rockcut Sculptures at Gadhelna

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